

Deliverable 1.2

Theoretical principles and methodological approach of the PHOEBE framework and selection of tools

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Project summary

The EU-funded 'Predictive Approaches for Safer Urban Environment' (PHOEBE) project aims to develop an integrated, dynamic human-centred predictive safety assessment framework in urban areas. This will be achieved by bringing together the interdisciplinary power of traffic simulation, road safety assessment, human behaviour, mode shift and induced demand modelling and new and emerging mobility data.

Focused on vulnerable road users' safety, the 3.5-year-long PHOEBE project will draw inspiration from real-world scenarios in the three pilot cities of Athens (GR), Valencia (ES) and West Midlands (UK). Testing activities will be performed across the use cases to simulate and forecast the impact of changes on safety in different scenarios of disruptions or transitions across urban transport networks.

Predicting and visualising the safety and socioeconomic outcomes of new forms of transport, new technologies, or regulatory and behavioural changes from the individual (micro) level up to the network-wide (macro) level will also be a significant game-changer for urban stakeholders. The results of PHOEBE can be used as a blueprint by other European cities to develop their knowledge products, such as socioeconomic analysis model, urban road safety assessment, human behaviour and choice modelling.

PHOEBE pilot cities

List of participating cities:

- Athens (Greece)
- Valencia (Spain)
- West Midlands (United Kingdom)

Social Links:

- https://twitter.com/Project_PHOEBE
- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/phoebe-project/>
- <https://www.youtube.com/@phoebeproject>

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Project partners

Organisation	Country	Abbreviation
EVROPSKI INSTITUT ZA OCENJEVANJE CEST - EURORAP	SI	EIRA
ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	EL	NTUA
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT	NL	TUD
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	DE	TUM
AIMSUN SLU	ES	AIM
POLIS AISBL	BE	POLIS
FACTUAL CONSULTING SL	ES	FC
UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA	ES	UPV
OSEVEN SINGLE MEMBER PRIVATE COMPANY	EL	O7
THE FLOW LIMITED	UK	FLOOW
INTERNATIONAL ROAD ASSESSMENT PROGRAMME	UK	iRAP

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
AADT	Average annual daily traffic
ADC	Average difference of cost
ADE	Average difference of unit of effectiveness
API	Application programming interface
AV	Automated vehicle
BCR	Benefit-cost ratio
CBA	Cost-benefit analysis
CF	Calibration factor
CEA	Cost-effectiveness analysis
CMF	Crash modification factor
DR	Deceleration rate
EVT	Extreme value theory
EAI	External agent interface
FHWA	Federal Highway Administration (US)
FSI	Fatal and serious injury
GTFS	General transit feed specification
ICER	Incremental cost effectiveness ratio
KPI	Key performance indicator
LMV	Light mobility vehicle (micro-mobility)
LOC	Loss of control (crash type)
ML	Machine learning
NPV	Net-present value
OSM	Open Street Map
PET	Post-encroachment time
PR	Percentage reduction
SEA	Socio-economic analysis
SEM	Structural equation model
SSM	Surrogate safety measure
SRS	Star Rating score
TD	Travel diaries
TTC	Time to collision
ViDA	iRAP's computational platform
Vol	Value of injury
VoSL	Value of statistical life
VoT	Value of time
VRU	Vulnerable road users
WTP	Willingness-to-pay

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the overall methodological framework in PHOEBE and provides the theoretical principles and methodological approaches pertaining to each component within the framework including:

- Demand models;
- Traffic microsimulation;
- Behavioural models;
- Road safety assessment; and
- Socioeconomic impact assessment.

Using the knowledge obtained from the literature reviews and stakeholder surveys in deliverable D1.1, a matrix and a flowchart are developed to define 'how' and in what 'process' the above components relate to one another. This back and forth *giving-receiving* notion is used as the main building block of the methodology which encompasses of the required data, processes, models, and testing requirements, as well as **how** the components interact with each other through input-output flow. Finally, the technical development preparation is also described within the deliverable for the implementation of the framework.

The **Demand Models** primarily focus on mode choice modelling (developing discrete choice models) by considering different modes of transport. These models use data from stated preference surveys, revealed preference data, and sociodemographic data as well as risk scores from the road safety assessment component within the PHOEBE framework. The outcome from mode choice modelling is incorporated as mode choice probabilities into **Traffic Microsimulation**.

Similar to the demand models, behavioural models in PHOEBE are initially estimated using empirical data as well. These models are divided into three general groups:

- **Group #1:** illegal behaviours of motorised road users (e.g. speeding);
- **Group #2:** illegal behaviours of non-motorised road users (e.g. illegal pedestrian crossing);
- **Group #3:** harsh manoeuvring (e.g. acceleration, deceleration, and cornering) of drivers / cyclists / e-scooters.

The input data for the behavioural models come from actual observed behaviours (in use cases) as well as survey questionnaires. These models with various analytical forms from discrete choice models to structural equation and other probabilistic models, provide the **Traffic Microsimulation** with the likelihood of unsafe and/or non-complying (to traffic laws and regulations) behaviours of the road users prioritised within PHOEBE project.

Traffic Microsimulation is one of the core components in PHOEBE combining the input from demand models and behavioural models to simulate and forecast the safety impacts of changes and future scenarios across urban transport networks. Starting from the data needed to model the study network through the network details (geometric, traffic control and other characteristics), demand data, vehicle kinematics based behavioural parameters etc., the **Traffic Microsimulation** component will further utilise input from human factor based behavioural models enabling more realistic capturing of the interactions between different road users (vehicles, cyclists, pedestrians, micro-mobility users).

The output from **Traffic Microsimulation** will further provide input to two components including **Road Safety Assessment** and **Behavioural Modelling**. **Road Safety Assessment** will take updated flows and speeds from **Traffic Microsimulation** for dynamic risk scores calculation.

On the other hand, the **Behavioural Models**, after post-processing of the simulated trajectories from **Traffic Microsimulation** to identify conflicts (critical interactions), will use conflicts and other necessary

data such as geometric, traffic, and observed crash data in the suitable models (e.g. Bayesian and EVT models), for estimating calibration parameters for **Road Safety Assessment**.

Based on the updated input from **Traffic Microsimulation** and **Behavioural Modelling**, **Road Safety Assessment** provides updated estimates of the risk scores making the assessment framework dynamic.

Within the deliverable, a list of safety indicators is also provided for the safety assessment and to compare different scenarios (baseline vs. future). Further, socioeconomic analysis methodology is also outlined for analysing and comparing the safety impacts between different evaluation scenarios.

The technical preparation part within this deliverable also further explores and identifies the models, extensions and capabilities within microsimulation modelling tools to incorporate the aforementioned (human factors based) behavioural models through necessary coding through Application Programming Interface (API). Additionally, it is also recognised how the dynamic risk scores from **Road Safety Assessment** will be used in **Traffic Microsimulation** for visualisation purposes.

The PHOEBE framework will be implemented through three pilot cities including Athens (GR), Valencia (ES), and West Midlands (UK) through testing different urban mobility scenarios. Additionally, through research and development (R&D) part of the project, further refinement and enhancement of the models within the framework is envisioned for broader use.

Progress beyond the state of the art

This section includes a summary of how, why and more precisely to what extent the work reported in the deliverable goes beyond the state of the art and play in its focus area.

The PHOEBE methodology that will be explained in this deliverable goes beyond the state of the art in integrating five transport components that have been studied and implemented discretely before (travel demand, traffic microsimulation, human behaviour, road safety assessment, and socio-economic analysis) into one scalable framework that systematically links microscopic with mesoscopic road safety assessment, and scaling it up to the entire network of a city (i.e. macroscopic). Investigating this integration within the PHOEBE methodology includes the following aspects:

- i. What information (data) each component receives from the other components;
- ii. What models each component applies on the received information from other components;
- iii. What information (data) each component provides for the other components; and
- iv. What process (order) is followed for the above information receiving / giving.

An important part of this integrated framework is creating a set of common safety indicators across all components and harmonising them so that the links between the components are seamless. In addition and during the development of this framework, special attention is given to the vulnerable road users (VRUs) and new emerging modes of transport (e.g. micro-mobility). Moreover, the framework is designed to receive feedback about the impact of a change that occurs in a transport network and adjust accordingly. This impact is assess in terms of health and safety, environmental and economic impacts.

Finally, the framework does not only include the theoretical underpinnings of the methodology but also the technical specifications that are required to implement the methodology in the existing tools (e.g. AIMSUN and iRAP) and apply them on use cases in PHOEBE.

Structure of the deliverable and links with other work packages/deliverables

The deliverable consists of 5 chapters. Chapter 1 presents the theoretical principles and methodological approaches behind the PHOEBE framework and explains 'how' the components within the framework interact with each other, including:

- Demand models;
- Traffic microsimulation;
- Behavioural models;
- Road safety assessment; and
- Socioeconomic impact assessment.

Chapter 2 provides further details on the models within each of the first four components presented above, input and output data, as well as the processes involved in the model development and/or interacting with other relevant components within the PHOEBE framework. The associated description on the fifth component (Socioeconomic Impact Assessment) is exclusively presented under Chapter 3 of the deliverable. Chapter 4 further discusses the technical aspects and solution requirements with respect to implementing the models (within the relevant PHOEBE components) into AIMSUN microsimulation and iRAP road safety assessment tools. Finally, a summary of what this deliverable achieves, establishes and sets out with respect to the future work in the project, is provided under the Conclusions in Chapter 5.

The extent of the details covered in this deliverable are related to the overall methodology of the PHOEBE framework meaning that the description within the deliverable primarily covers the theoretical details on the methods/models under each component within the framework along with their interaction with each other. The details on how different methods/models within each of the above components will be practically implemented in the relevant tools (e.g. AIMSUN microsimulation and iRAP road safety assessment), will be provided in PHOEBE Work Packages 3 (**Model development and enhancement**) and 4 (**Safety use-case implementation**).

Finally, it is worth mentioning that the PHOEBE methodological framework (the 'HOW' matrix together with the process flowchart) serves two purposes: (i) to be a new research and development (R&D) framework that advances the state-of-the-art and can be used by other researchers and scholars for dynamically performing the road safety assessments through integrating the existing, emerging, and future changes within the demand models, traffic microsimulation, behavioural models, and road safety assessment models; and (ii) to be a "blueprint" for how cities can establish and apply the predictive safety assessment framework efficiently and cost-effectively, providing a practical guide on how it works and how to implement it through the knowledge products such as socioeconomic analysis model, urban road safety assessment, human behaviour and demand modelling.

1 Theoretical principles & methodological approaches

1.1 Research questions and objectives

The PHOEBE Framework is a methodological approach designed for cities to better understand the future safety implications of changes in the transport systems, such as changes in road user behaviours, the redesign or creation of new infrastructure, or the introduction of a new mode. It aims to be a “blueprint” for how cities can establish and apply the predictive safety assessment framework efficiently and cost-effectively.

To do so, it aims to bring together several existing elements currently used in transport planning, assessment and modelling, including:

- Travel demand and mode shift models, which can predict consumer choices and road user flow changes;
- Traffic simulation environments, which provide insights into how these various elements interact in virtual traffic scenarios;
- Human behaviour models which can help anticipate how road users respond in given scenarios, and the extent to which they may deviate from typical behaviours;
- Road safety assessment, which can provide objective measures of road user safety linked to speed, flow and the physical road features; and
- Socio-economic impact assessment which can understand the health, safety, economic and environmental impacts of changes in the transport system.

The PHOEBE Framework brings these elements together to enable analysis on the combined effect of future changes, as well as how they evolve over time. The development of the PHOEBE Framework involves three principal aspects:

- 1 The **theoretical developments**, which includes the research, where necessary, for key principles and methodology of the Framework. These include, for example, how forecast safety impacts can be extrapolated across a city-wide network.
- 2 The **technical developments** required to ensure that each component of the Framework has the necessary functionality to produce the analysis required. This includes, for example, the model developments to allow safety ratings to be incorporated into traffic simulation.
- 3 The **tools and materials** required for the use and exploitation of the Framework for its intended end users, to ensure the Framework can be utilised for its stated purpose and meet its desired objective. The PHOEBE Framework thus needs to ultimately be a practical guide on how it works and how to implement it.

This deliverable is the output of the PHOEBE Project Tasks 1.2 (proposition for the dynamic risk assessment methodology), 1.3 (socioeconomic analysis methodology) & 1.4 (technical development preparation). It aims to address *how* the following **research and technical aspects required for the development of the PHOEBE Framework** will be achieved, namely:

- How to model mode shift and induced demand for new modes of transport and extrapolate it to network-level;
- How to integrate vrus into traffic microsimulation environments, more accurately and more comprehensively (in terms of their safety);
- How to incorporate the pertinent behavioural models into traffic microsimulation environments;
- How to make use of traffic microsimulation and create suitable safety indicators for the creation of dynamic safety outputs in road safety assessment;
- How to conduct a socio-economic analysis of the safety impacts; and
- How to determine the technical methods, resources and tools needed to deliver the technical aspects of the project and achieve the integration of the above aspects (including technical specifications and related inter-dependencies).

It is important to note that while the research and development part of the Framework may include a broad range of data/models for each of the five components in PHOEBE, not all of them may ultimately be implemented in PHOEBE. Only those that are relevant and feasible (particularly with an eye on the use case needs) will be implemented.

Figure 1-1 shows how the different elements of the PHOEBE are linked with one another in an integrated framework.

Figure 1-1 The dynamic dimension of the PHOEBE framework

As discussed in the state-of-the-art and end user needs review report of PHOEBE (Deliverable 1.1), the PHOEBE Framework spans different levels of analysis (micro-, meso- and macroscopic). Figure 1-2 shows, conceptually, how each element connects with these levels.

Figure 1-2 The multilevel dimension of the PHOEBE framework

As the PHOEBE Framework works to systematise the integration of these elements, the project team has identified several focus questions to guide its research and technical developments. These are:

- What information needs to be provided by mode share and induced demand models to inform the dynamic simulation framework? How can changes in demand or new modes be modelled?
- What are the entry points of traffic simulation models to receive input for the dynamic risk assessment – how can induced demand and behavioural models be introduced into traffic simulation?
- How can new modes of transport and other intervention scenarios in urban areas be modelled in traffic simulation environments?
- What behavioural models are best suited for considering the most critical behaviours of road users with potential safety impacts? How can behavioural changes be linked to safety outputs?
- How can road safety assessment be calculated ‘dynamically’, that is, for different traffic speeds and flows over the course of a day?
- How can the finer spatial dimensions of traffic simulation be integrated with the mesoscopic safety assessment from road safety assessment models?
- What safety indicators are needed to estimate socio-economic impacts of policies and changes in the transport network? How can the PHOEBE Framework provide these indicators?

To address the questions, it is necessary to understand the required data, models and processes that are within each element that make up the PHOEBE Framework, as well as the relationship between the components. This includes: the input data and entry points; all models to be applied on the data coming through those entry points; and the outputs of those models.

To assist with this, a matrix in Figure 1-3 maps the targeted data, models and processes into the five main components of PHOEBE: demand models, traffic microsimulation, behavioural models, road safety assessment and socio-economic impact assessment. The matrix is reinforced by the analysis scale in each component (micro, meso and macro).

Figure 1-3 The “how” matrix of data, models and processes in PHOEBE methodology

The matrix shows **how** each component is interrelated with other components (i.e., what inputs it receives from other components, what models it applies on those inputs, and what outputs it gives to other components) and **how** the predictive safety assessment moves from micro to meso to macro scales of analysis and the other way around (i.e., scalability). Hence, the matrix is referred to as the *How Matrix*.

1.1.1 The How Matrix explained

Starting from the top left cell in the matrix, the demand models take several inputs as explanatory variables to compute travel demand and provide this demand in terms of OD matrices and mode choice probabilities to traffic microsimulation (PDM₁₂). In return, traffic microsimulation provides updated inputs or explanatory variables due to the changes to the demand models to re-calculate the travel demand, including the induced demand (PDM₂₁).

This back and forth giving and receiving occur for other components in PHOEBE too. However, there may be no direct exchange between some components in the framework. For example, demand models will

not directly provide any inputs to behavioural models, road safety assessment and socioeconomic impact assessment and hence the corresponding cells in the matrix (PDM₁₃, PDM₁₄ and PDM₁₅) are greyed out.

Traffic microsimulation provides surrogate safety measures as proactive indicators of safety to behavioural models (PDM₂₃) and dynamic flow and speed to road safety assessment (PDM₂₄). There is no direct link between traffic microsimulation and socioeconomic impact assessment (PDM₂₅ and PDM₅₂), or between behavioural models and socioeconomic impact assessment (PDM₃₅ and PDM₅₃).

While behavioural models will not give any direct input to demand models (PDM₃₁), they provide traffic microsimulation with the likelihood of road user behaviours (PDM₃₂) and road safety assessment with behavioural FSI values (PDM₃₄). Road safety assessment is the only component in PHOEBE that will give input to all other components. It will provide static safety assessment of roads (for example, risk scores) to demand models (PDM₄₁), traffic microsimulation (PDM₄₂), and behavioural models (PDM₄₃). It also provides the socioeconomic analysis with final FSI estimations (PDM₃₄₅) based on dynamic safety assessment. In return, the socioeconomic analysis will give the overall impact assessment back to the demand models (PDM₅₁) to adjust the demand after an intervention has been implemented.

In the following sections, details of the above data (input and output), models and processes in each component are explained, and the inter-relationship between the cells in the How Matrix are then discussed. The result of consolidating the data, models, processes and the inter-relationship between PHOEBE components is then the integrated scalable framework.

2 The PHOEBE Framework

2.1 Overview

The PHOEBE Framework assembles existing tools and models in such a manner that, with the required amendments to their inputs and outputs, they can exchange information to forecast the impacts on road safety more precisely, with emphasis on vulnerable road users (VRU). In addition to the research and technological developments required to connect the PHOEBE Framework elements, the incorporation of VRU into some of these elements requires dedicated attention.¹

Figure 2-1 shows in detail how these interconnections work. It is important to note it does not delve into the particularities of each component. These particularities will be discussed in the following sections.

The input data within each component include necessary data from external sources and from other components within the PHOEBE Framework. Although depicted in Step 1, the external data inputs are assumed to be available, collected, cleaned and standardised before the process start (as in any typical road safety evaluation/calculation process).

Specifically, the data inputs for each component (from outside the other PHOEBE components) include the following:

- 1 Data for road safety assessment includes that relevant to prediction of future crashes such as historic crash data, operational traffic flow data (speeds, flows or similar – e.g. occupancies), geometrical and infrastructure/network characteristics data such as the number of lanes on the roads, presence of cycle lanes, pedestrian crossings, bus stops, traffic signals etc.
- 2 Data for mode choice and induced demand models includes that relevant for mode choice and travel demand modelling, such as socio-demographic data, land-use data, network data, data from origin-destination (OD) surveys, etc.
- 3 Data for the behavioural modelling requires human factors based behavioural data, such as counts of specific behavioural instances (e.g. distraction, speeding illegal crossings), related geometric, network & infrastructure data, relevant crash data and pertinent survey data.
- 4 Data for the traffic microsimulation includes that needed for modelling the study area including network characteristics (geometric layout, transport features (e.g. pedestrian crosswalks, functional attributes, configurations, etc.), traffic demand and compositions, traffic control data, vehicular kinematics, etc.

¹ VRU-specific aspects are present in all elements, such as behavioural modelling, traffic simulation and road safety analysis (especially with surrogate crash measures). However, the VRU particularities, in data and real conditions, will be handled internally as they are encountered within each of the elements and are not discussed here.

Figure 2-1 The PHOEBE Framework flowchart

It should be noted that overlap exists across the data needs of each element. The similarities in data types can often serve for validation across data sources, and verification that the same areas are described with the same signs and magnitudes across databases (e.g. for geometric data). In latter stages of the Framework, the sources that are deemed as most accurate and most complete will be selected and used exclusively, while the others will be retained for comparison and reference purposes in data frames.

The following sub-sections further provide a summary of the individual steps within the framework, the components involved, and their interaction with each other while sections 3 and 4 delve into more theoretical details on the models within each component as well as the input-output flow from one to the other component within the framework. The details of how the models will be implemented in the respective tools (i.e. AIMSUN microsimulation and iRAP road safety assessment) will be covered in WP3.

Finally, the PHOEBE predictive safety assessment framework will measure the impacts (KPIs) over the present or a baseline year and in future after implementing the changes, over some time frame (e.g. in 5, 10, 15 years, or longer time period), to account for the changes in the network through introduction of interventions, regulations, behaviours, or new technologies etc., and even if there are no such changes, to simply account for the naturally occurring changes in future such as through the population growth or travel patterns.

Historical trends such as population growth, tourism growth, pre-existing trends in mode choice and/or travel patterns, land use changes, etc. can be used for baseline forecasts. For projections in any future baseline scenario, an annual multiplier factors based on historical data or estimates will be required. Consideration must be given to any skewness in the data due to any reasons e.g. impact of the global pandemic. The precise forecasting or planning horizon will be decided later in forthcoming work packages (WP3 and WP4).

2.1.1 Step 1 – Baseline calculations

The purpose of Step 1 in the flowchart is to accurately capture the existing baseline scenario (the current situation). The baseline scenario is the reference point against which the impact of any future changes can be compared (Figure 2-2).

Step 1 Baseline scenario (without any changes)

Figure 2-2 The PHOEBE Framework flowchart – Step 1

In this step, data passes between each of the elements as follows:

- Road safety assessment provides static road safety crash risk and crash occurrence estimates by segment to the mode choice and behavioural modelling.
- Mode choice modelling (incl. induced demand) provides mode choice probabilities and behavioural modelling provides probabilities of specific behaviour occurrence to traffic microsimulation.
- After the traffic microsimulation runs, the traffic microsimulation provides simulated trajectories of the road users which (through post-processing in a surrogate safety assessment model) provides number of conflicts to the behavioural modelling. It also provides flow and speed data to road safety assessment.
- The behavioural modelling provides the fatal and severe injury (FSI) calibration parameters to road safety assessment for calculating the updated safety ratings (Star Ratings) for variable speed and flows (“dynamic Star Ratings”).
- Road safety assessment provides updated Star Ratings per segment to the traffic microsimulation for visualisation of dynamic risk.
- The core outputs from Step 1 of the PHOEBE Framework are the KPIs received from the traffic microsimulation and road safety assessment to be used for scenario comparison.

2.1.2 Step 2 – scenario change calculations

In Step 2, road safety (or other transport-oriented) changes are assumed to have been implemented in the study areas. Step 2 receives inputs comparable to those of Step 1 to conduct the necessary calculations for the KPIs *after* taking the specific changes (e.g. infrastructure, regulatory, behavioural, etc.) into account (Figure 2-3).

Figure 2-3 The PHOEBE Framework flowchart – Step 2

Step 2 is separated in two stages:

- 1 Scenario set-up: Establishing the scenario which primarily involves setting up for the mode choice component considering intervention; and
- 2 Scenario evaluation: Similar to step 1, but now with the changes in the transport network.

These are described further in the following sections. Step 2 may rerun calculations based on the outcome of Step 3 (the Benefit-Cost Ratio of changes). The changes may be redesigned if they are not considered cost-effective. Therefore, in the flowchart, steps 2 & 3 can be considered a 'feedback loop'.

Scenario set-up involves the following steps:

- 1 The four data inputs of step 1 are updated based on the proposed changes, and relevant updated inputs are provided to the mode choice modelling component.
- 2 The traffic microsimulation, after incorporating the changes in the models and running the simulation, provides updated outputs relevant for the mode choice modelling and road safety assessment.
- 3 Road safety assessment calculates the updated risk scores after incorporating the changes and relevant updated output from the traffic microsimulation, to be used for the mode choice modelling.

During scenario evaluation, updated inputs from traffic microsimulation and road safety assessment flow to mode choice modelling (with changes) which then flow to the other elements. The four updated elements (with changes) run their respective internal calculations. Several processes then occur as each element provides outputs to others, and to the updated KPIs for scenario comparison. Specifically:

- Road safety assessment provides dynamic road safety crash risk and crash occurrence estimates by segment to the mode choice modelling and to the behavioural modelling.
- Behavioural modelling provides FSI crash calibration factors to the road safety assessment, and probabilities of specific behaviour occurrence to traffic microsimulation.
- Traffic microsimulation provides post-processing of the trajectories and the number of conflicts to behavioural modelling and flow and speed data to road safety assessment.
- Road safety assessment provides updated Star Ratings per segment to the previously calculated KPIs (having taken the changes into account) and traffic microsimulation.
- Finally, traffic microsimulation provides the core outputs of step 2, which is the updated KPI outputs of the intervention case, after comparing them with the baseline scenario.

2.1.3 Step 3 – Socioeconomic analysis

Step 3, the socioeconomic analysis, involves conducting a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) by utilising the output from the two previous steps. This step is critical as it will determine if further iterations are required, starting the process of step 2 again (starting with setting up a new scenario).

Step 3 Socioeconomic analysis

Figure 2-4 The PHOEBE Framework flowchart – Step 3

The socioeconomic analysis uses the KPIs from the baseline scenario (Step 1) and from the future scenario accounting for changes (Step 2) and upscales them for the entire network. The upscaling process is explicitly described in the following sub-section.

Unit benefits which represent the value of all crashes and injuries, are estimated through a ‘willingness-to-pay’ model (based on localised interviews), which is then used to calculate the cost of reducing traffic risk.

The scaled-up baseline KPIs, intervention KPIs and unit benefits are then used as input to estimate the total network benefits or disbenefits due to the proposed changes, in terms of road safety and monetised outcomes (e.g. casualties prevented, costs mitigated).

The cost of the proposed changes is estimated based on (i) one-time investment costs, (ii) recurring investment costs and (iii) other costs associated. As a general rule, the higher number of external costs that can be accurately forecasted and included, the more accurate the CBA is at societal scales. A common reference year must be established, in which all costs are brought to while taking the projected future values into account (by anticipating future inflation values). It is important to consider correct units of analysis for each intervention, as a CBA represents the dimensions of the area which the intervention affects, and for which the CBA was conducted (Daniels et al., 2019). The estimated costs are also upscaled for the entire network, to be on the same reference frame as the others.

It is important to note that all the possible changes in the costs and benefits over time occurring inherently and/or resulting from the short and long-term measures, will be incorporated within the socioeconomic analysis component. In order to either base the core Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) calculations or augment their output, an array of network-level indicators will also be considered within the presented framework. These actions can be performed by considering two main pathways:

A) Integration in road safety effects induced by network changes

The percentage of changes in crashes, especially those of more significant injury severity (i.e. Fatal & Serious Injury Crashes – FSI) is a critical parameter defining the core part of the human costs of crashes, and constitute the bedrock of the road safety effects for the CBA. As the human costs are largely based on willingness-to-pay investigations, the monetary expression of this parameter may also change based on changes of the related societal perceptions.

Wherever crashes have not occurred, or there are no data available, a number of proxy data (also known as surrogate safety measures) can be used to obtain provisional numbers, such as the number of harsh events (brakings/accelerations) per segment, the Time-To-Collision (TTC) per vehicle or the percentage of travel at 3-star rated (or better) by road user type per road axis.

B) Integration in costs/benefits incurred by network changes

Alternatively, interventions in a network can provide public health and environmental positive effects that can be translated to economic benefits without being directly related to road safety, thus influencing the outputs of road infrastructure-oriented CBA in terms of benefits rather than costs.

Indicatively, the network-aggregated quality-adjusted life years due to uptake of active modes and changes in air quality can be considered, as can the increase of modal share of walking, cycling & other forms of more active mobility activities. Percentage changes of motorised and non-motorised trips are a similar indicator, although it is preferable to compare and evaluate them also within a general demand context as well (e.g. Has overall traffic throughput fluctuated in absolute based on the network changes or not?).

Additionally, percentage changes in CO₂/NO_x/PM₁₀ emissions and/or fuel consumption can be monetised in public health and economic benefits and taken into account by the CBA as well.

Wider benefits can also be included, though they are more challenging to determine. Specifically, health sector savings from reduced injury cases, less stress in the system, lower maintenance and personnel costs. Wider benefits might also include personal or household savings resulting from uptake of active modes as well.

The output of the CBA step, includes Net-Present Value (NPV) Analysis and Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA). The output of this analysis determines whether the proposed changes have a true positive outcome for the areas that they are implemented in, and approach the magnitude of the benefits. In strict terms, the Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) is expressed as a fraction, and, if it is over 1.00, the measures are considered beneficial. In practice, a low BCR (e.g. 1.05) may not be considered desirable. In that case, several options/scenarios (with changes) can be compared so that the one with the highest BCR can be chosen for a given area.

As previously mentioned, the PHOEBE Framework features a loop mechanism for activation in any case where a specific measure (change) is examined, and does not yield a satisfactory BCR. These changes are reflected in the data and new inputs are provided (based on the changes) at the start of Step 2 – Stage. Then the process starts over until a satisfactory BCR has been determined, giving the overall PHOEBE framework a dynamic nature.

2.1.3.1 Scaling techniques

Scaling is a process meriting consideration, especially considering the nature of each indicator. There are many ways to approach it, and it can really be considered an 'art' for specific variables, especially where data is scarce. Each variable and component have their own particularities when it comes to scaling, therefore the final decision lies with the analyst handling the data.

A key difference is whether the data in question are point-type data (such as those from roadside observations) or continuous data. Continuous data can have smoother transitions and interpolations between measuring locations are typically easier. As this data are spread across a network, their locations (or the centroids of the corresponding segments) can be depicted on a spatial table. The table contains weights that denotes how each location is influenced by the others, based on proximity (Moran, 1950).

There have been several proposed geographical criteria for the specification of spatial weights. Some alternatives are, indicatively:

- Common border binary criterion: Weights of neighbouring locations with common borders are 1, the rest are 0 – a variation also exists in the form of k-nearest neighbour criterion.
- Critical distance binary criterion: Weights of neighbouring locations within a certain distance are 1, the rest are 0.
- Shared edge distance criterion: Weights of neighbouring locations are assigned based on the length of a shared edge length among locations.
- Distance decay function criterion: Weights of neighbouring locations are assigned based on the distance of centroids from the location of interest, with more distant locations being reduced by an inverse distance function.

Several other weighting functions exist in the literature (e.g. Bertazon & Elikan, 2009). However, it is commonly understood that the construction of the weighting matrix with a particular criterion, or, in other terms, by the application of a particular weighting function, should be based on the underlying theory of the phenomenon at hand.

As an example, when considering the extrapolation of average speeds in locations with no data for road safety applications, road type should be considered. Therefore, within a city section, a dedicated matrix with segment centroids should be created, for (i) primary – arterial roads, (ii) secondary – collector roads and (iii) tertiary – residential roads (and so on with any reasonable grouping), and extrapolation should only be conducted among roads of the same type. The categorisation of spatial scale of each of the variables beforehand (e.g. Ziakopoulos & Yannis, 2020) and the decision on how much they can be affected across space (e.g. affected by adjacent roads only, by closer neighbouring roads, by the entire network and everything in between).

Another avenue is to conduct statistical or machine learning (ML) modelling with the variable in question as the dependent variable, which will be then correlated with known independent variables that have data available in the areas to be scaled. The calibrated models can then project predictions in unknown areas. However, it should be noted that such models do not have spatial effects incorporated, and only use their non-spatial counterparts. Relevant results show good accuracy for harsh event data (Ziakopoulos et al., 2022).

It should be noted that micro and macro simulation processes and results can be evaluated in terms of their transferability, as noted by Sha et al. (2022). This is achieved by conducting statistical modelling to existing results and defining a functional relationship between PCU factors and contributing parameters. The PCU relationship is provided as input to the volume-delay functions (VDF) of macroscopic demand models to forecast the potential macroscopic implications on the network performance induced by different AV penetration rates.

It is important to have an overarching protocol within the PHOEBE project. As such, inverse-distance weighting can be selected as the default method to be used with all variables until determined otherwise by the analyst handling the data. In cases of point-type data with low measurements (e.g. illegal pedestrian crossing), it is reasonable to assume an average value which the point-type measurements taper off to after close distance (e.g. strictly adjacent streets). This is the spatial equivalent to the imputation-to-the-mean technique often used in ML.

2.2 Demand models

Generating the mode choice probabilities, modal shift, and consequently the travel demand containing the induced travel demand in terms of OD matrices (classified under the modes of transport) are critical elements of the PHOEBE Framework. The whole component can be termed demand modelling since it not only contains mode choice modelling but also has an antecedent part (to the mode choice modelling) of procuring the OD matrices (most likely from the destination choice step of the macroscopic travel demand models of the use cases or some other relevant sources) and the descendant part of generating the travel demand including the induced travel demand in the form of OD matrices classified under the modes of transport to be considered in PHOEBE. The details of the mode choice modelling process are explained in the succeeding section.

As discussed above, the mode choice model is the most essential element in the demand modelling component of the PHOEBE Framework. The outputs of these model(s), the mode choice probabilities and mode shift percentages, are the foundation of the overall PHOEBE's methodological framework. In addition to the mode choice models, the demand modelling component will contain models to estimate the induced travel demand (identification of the characteristics of the new trips). These models resemble the mode choice models (described in the succeeding sections) and depend on household travel surveys to forecast the induced travel demand (Kalliga, 2021).

The demand modelling component of the PHOEBE Framework involves the following steps as defined by Barff et al. (1982) and Narayanan & Antoniou (2023):

- 1 **Data collection:** Data collection is the most crucial part of the demand modelling component since the demand forecast's quality depends on the input data's quality.
- 2 **Model (Mode choice models and models for induced demand) estimation:** A process to determine the parameters' values and relationships that describe the mode choice and new trips (induced demand) based on specific characteristics, e.g., sociodemographic, socioeconomic and land use characteristics of a given area.
- 3 **Model calibration:** Readjusting the parameters' (estimated before) values and characteristics to align the model outputs (forecasts) more accurately with observed real-world data. This step is performed after the estimation of the models.
- 4 **Model validation:** Assessing the mode choice forecasts, predictive accuracy and performance by comparing the forecasts with independent real-world data not used in the model's development. It is carried out in parallel with the model calibration process.
- 5 **Demand generation:** The actual travel demand (number of trips) categorised as per the modes of transport is generated by multiplying the outputs of the validated model by the consolidated travel demand (OD matrices) in the form of trips (coming from the trip distribution step of the macroscopic travel demand model of the region under investigation).

Based on the planning horizons (future scenarios), demand forecasts will be made using the historic data (e.g. population growth trends, land use changes etc.) also including the expected changes in travel behaviours over time and due to short- and long-term measures inducing changes in travel demand, mode

choice, and induced demand. The short-term measures include prompt or sudden measures, e.g., price changes and availability of usable alternatives. In contrast, long-term measures include measures that show effects in a prolonged period, e.g., socio-demographic changes and infrastructural measures (from inception to realisation). The models for computing travel demand, mode choice, and induced demand will contain the input variable addressing long- and short-term measures.

2.2.1 Processes

It is essential to delineate the correct usage of the models and the data, place these models in the correct flow and ensure precise linkage of these models with the other components of PHOEBE. The conceptual flowchart of mode choice modelling is presented in Figure 2-5.

The mode choice probabilities will be the basis of the succeeding calculations and modelling processes envisioned in the PHOEBE framework. Along with other data like geometric data, functional attributes, control plan data, and public transport data, the mode choice probabilities will be treated as the inputs of the succeeding processes or components: traffic microsimulation, behavioural modelling, and road safety assessment for the baseline scenario.

Figure 2-5 Mode choice modelling process in detail. Adapted from (Pestel et al., 2016)

Mode shift and induced demand reflect the flow changes and behavioural parameters used to calculate the FSI estimations. This facilitates the calculation of the differences in the predicted crash numbers resulting from the particular scenario. The forecast difference in the number of crashes (between the baseline and planned scenarios) are then scaled up for the whole network, forming an input to the socioeconomic analysis.

2.2.2 Data

Demand models (discrete choice models) use a wide range of data, such as stated preference surveys and revealed preference data, sociodemographic data, etc., as inputs (explanatory variables) to compute the output, i.e., mode choice or the probabilities of choosing each mode of transport.

When compared to the baseline scenario, the mode choices of different scenarios produce an important indicator called mode shift. The relevant inputs and outputs (data) of the mode choice modelling process are listed and described below (Department for Transport, 2014; Ortúzar & Willumsen, 2014).

2.2.2.1 Input data

The demand or mode choice models are sophisticated discrete choice models (statistical models) that can predict the mode choices and mode shifts. Three modelling steps are carried out to develop these models: model estimation, calibration, and validation (Department for Transport, 2020a). Specific data are used as input data to develop such discrete choice models (Department for Transport, 2020b; D. A. ; Hensher & Button, 2008; Ortúzar & Willumsen, 2014). This data is termed input data and are typically of the following types:

(Socio-)demographic data:

Demographic or sociodemographic data are the most crucial input dataset in demand modelling. This data provides essential information regarding the demography of the region under consideration, e.g., household structures, employment status, trip generation rates, car/other modes of transport ownership and availability trends, socioeconomic structure, and license holding (Department for Transport, 2020a), as depicted in the following Figure 2-6.

Figure 2-6 Sociodemographic data input requirements for demand models

Source/s: This data can be obtained from the regional or national census data, national travel surveys, or specialised local household (travel) surveys can be set up, especially for this purpose.

Land-use data

Land-use data ties the population data to the geographical dimension and enables the calculation of the trips spatially for doubly (work, education) and singly (shopping, leisure) constrained purposes for the considered person groups.

Source/s: This data can be obtained from the regional or national census, workplace statistics, and local authority planning data for residential, employee, retail, and commercial floorspace by zone.

Network data

Network data refers to datasets encompassing details of the network or the transport supply side. It provides the utilities, such as time, distance, etc., for the demand calculations. It also provides inputs about an essential mode of transport, e.g., frequency and headways of public transport, as well as road safety assessment risk scores.

Source/s: This data can be obtained from Open Street Map (OSM) and local public transport service providers. Often, public transport data are available in the form of GTFS datasets too. Road safety

assessment risk scores (including pre-existing data) can be derived from the existing road safety assessment tools for any region of interest.

Travel to zonal destinations by Purpose, Mode, and Time of Day (Period)

These datasets provide the trends concerning the destinations and the purpose of the trips, mode choices, and the times and costs of the trips. These trends are used to estimate the mode choice models. Thus, these datasets are considered critical for estimating the mode choice models.

Source/s: Principally specialised surveys, including the stated preference surveys and revealed preference. It can also be collected from sources, e.g., roadside interviews, mobile network data, automatic number plate recognition, and local/national/regional household travel surveys. Travel diaries (including longitudinal travel diaries) are also used to gather this data.

Explainer notes

Stated preference surveys (SP)

The SP survey (the Contingent Valuation) is a technique for establishing valuations between alternatives. The subject is asked to choose between policies, products, or services with desirable and undesirable characteristics. In doing so, they indirectly reveal which parts are most important to them. SP surveys are instrumental in cases without real-world data to make conclusions. In the following steps, detailed stated preference surveys will be designed and disseminated among the subjects of pilot cities (use cases) to collect the SP data. The SP data will facilitate the processes of the suitable demand model class choice and the estimation of the chosen models.

Revealed preference data (RP)

The RP data assumes consumers' purchasing (demand) habits reveal their preferences. RP data will be gathered from several sources, e.g., the actual purchase data (e.g., ticket purchases) and consumption or demand data (e.g., actual travel demand counts). The RP data will facilitate the demand model choice, estimation, and validation of the chosen demand models (mode choice models).

(Longitudinal) Travel diaries (TD)

Longitudinal travel diaries are records to study and track individuals' travel patterns and behaviours over an extended period. Unlike regular travel diaries that keep records for a specific period, i.e., a day or a week, longitudinal travel diaries collect information over several weeks, months, or years. Longitudinal travel diaries are a type of revealed preference survey. Thus, these data sources will capture the actual behaviour and choices of the respondents for specific contexts.

Trip lengths and times

Trip lengths and trip times are specialised datasets used indirectly in the mode choice model development process. This data is not used during the model estimation but in the model validation process. Trip lengths and times are often used with their spatial, temporal, and purpose contexts, i.e., in conjunction with the origin-destination, origin-destination times, and purpose of the trips.

Source/s: The local/regional/national household travel surveys are the chief sources of these datasets. In addition to these surveys, (longitudinal) travel diaries are also considered rich data sources.

Vehicle occupancies

Vehicle occupancies across all the person groups, purpose, and mode segments are noteworthy datasets used in demand modelling processes. These datasets are utilised to estimate the number of vehicles moving in the network. In addition to the number of vehicles, these datasets are also used to estimate the transport performance (subsequently the KPIs, e.g., emissions, consumptions, etc.) of the different modes of transport.

Data sources: The local/regional/national household travel surveys are the chief sources of these datasets. In addition to these surveys, (longitudinal) travel diaries are also considered.

Vehicle operating costs (generalised costs) and Value of Time (VoT)

The vehicle operating costs and the generalised costs of vehicle operation for different person groups and purposes of trips and the VoT are used to estimate the impedances arising while making trips between the origin-destination pairs in the demand modelling process.

Source/s: The vehicle operating, generalised costs, and the VoT are generally provided by local planning and statistical authorities. These values can also be estimated from the "travel to zonal destinations by Purpose, Mode, and Time of Day (Period)" datasets. Table 2-1 lists all the required data and their probable sources for demand modelling.

Table 2-1 Demand modelling data requirements and their sources

Nr.	Main dataset	Sub dataset	To be used in	Sources
1	Population	Household structure	Trip generation rate calculations	Regional or national census data National travel surveys Specialised local household (travel) surveys
1.1		Employment status	Socioeconomic and person group categorisation	
1.2		Trip generation rates	Mode split distribution	
1.3				
1.4		Socioeconomic structure		
1.5		License holding		
1.6	Cars and other modes of transport availability			
2	Land-use data		Trip generation Trip distribution Traffic Analysis Zone demarcation	Regional or national census Workplace Statistics Local authority planning data
3	Network data		Utility calculations Incorporation of transport supply side in calculations	Open Street Maps (OSM) Local authorities and public transport service providers
4	Travel to zonal destinations by Purpose, Mode, and Time of Day		Trip generation Trip distribution Time period choice Ascertaining trends	Specialised travel surveys including stated preference surveys. Revealed preferences Travel diaries
5	Trip lengths and times		Model calibration Model validation	Specialised travel surveys Travel diaries
6	Vehicle occupancies		Estimation of the number of vehicles	Specialised travel surveys

Nr.	Main dataset	Sub dataset	To be used in	Sources
			Estimation of transport performances Estimation of KPIs, e.g., emissions, consumptions etc.	Travel diaries
7	Vehicle operating costs (generalised cost) and Value of time (VoT)		Estimation of utilities and disutilities. Estimation of impedances.	Local planning and statistical authorities Travel surveys Travel diaries

2.2.2.2 Output data

The demand model generates specific output data. The main outputs are described as follows.

Estimated mode choice probabilities

Mode choice probabilities, as the outputs of a mode choice model, represent the likelihood or probability that a group of individuals will choose for a specific purpose, a specific transportation mode (such as walking, bike, car, or public transit) among the available options for a given trip, based on their characteristics and the attributes of the modes. These probabilities add up to 1 (Figure 2-7), indicating that one of the modes will be chosen for the trip.

These probabilities are essential in understanding and predicting mode choices in travel demand modelling. A higher probability for a particular mode suggests that the model predicts a greater likelihood that individuals will choose that mode for the given trip, considering the specified factors and attributes.

Figure 2-7 Mode choice probabilities

Estimated mode splits

Individual mode choice probabilities associated with specific modes of transport can be interpreted as mode split amongst all the available modes. Mode split can be further used to generate mode shift.

Mode shifts

A change in the input variables of the mode choice models, e.g., travel time, cost, etc., will develop a new mode split or mode share; thus, the baseline mode share can be compared with the new share to calculate mode shift.

Estimated OD movements (trips) matrices including the induced travel demand

The mode share or split can be used to generate the OD movements in terms of the trips categorised by modes of transport. These trip matrices can be derived by multiplying the OD trip matrices obtained from the trip distribution calculations with the mode choice probabilities. In addition to the regular OD matrices, the (discrete choice) model estimated for forecasting the induced demand will also generate the OD matrices of the induced travel demand in terms of the number of new trips added due to the changes introduced (Kalliga, 2021).

Demand elasticities

For a given scenario (i.e., a different set of input variables compared to the baseline situation), the outputs of the mode choice models can be used to generate demand elasticities. These demand elasticities help understand the changes of the dependent variables under the changing magnitude of the independent or explanatory variables.

$$e = \frac{\log(T^1) - \log(T^0)}{\log(C^1) - \log(C^0)} \quad (2-1)$$

Where,

e is the elasticity,

T is the demand with superscripts 0 and 1 indicating the values before and after the change of cost,

C is the cost with superscripts 0 and 1 indicating the values before and after costs.

2.2.3 Theoretical basis

In PHOEBE, the development of suitable discrete choice models is envisioned for large-scale forecasting of the mode shift (M. E. Ben-Akiva & Lerman, 2006). The estimation of more complicated models, such as hybrid class models (models with latent variables) and latent class choice models are also envisioned to forecast specific entities such as experience and effects of external factors like real-time information flows through the internet and apps. These models will be developed as per the three steps (estimated, calibrated, and validated). The relevant parts of such models will be considered in the project's discrete choice model, which will be planned for large-scale forecasting.

The primary aims of the choice model development are listed below:

- 1 Forecasting the large-scale mode choice and mode shift by different person groups (Ben-Akiva & Lerman, 2006; Domencich & McFadden, 1975);
- 2 Incorporating various modes of transport in the model (Domencich & McFadden, 1975);
- 3 Incorporating specific intangible properties in the form of input (latent) variables in the model (Motoaki & Daziano, 2015); and

- 4 Incorporating the latent class choice models to capture observed and unobserved heterogeneity. These models can relate a set of observed discrete multivariate variables to a set of latent variables (variables that are not directly observed but are rather inferred) (García-Melero et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2003).

Most of the modelling process depends on the input data (explained in the preceding sections) and the SP/RP surveys. The final model type and modelling processes will be thus finalised after the completion of the input data collection, including the completion of the SP/RP surveys. A generalised model representation is given below:

Explainer notes

Generalised discrete choice model for forecasting mode choice (Ben-Akiva & Lerman, 2006)

A discrete choice model works within the foundational assumption of rational choices the individual (groups) makes when confronted with a discrete set of alternatives to maximise their benefit or utility. The discrete choice evaluates the input or explanatory variables concerning the characteristics of the user groups and the available alternatives. The choice is expressed in terms of probability. The generalised form of the discrete choice model is presented below:

$$P_{ij} = f(S_i, X_j) \quad (2-2)$$

Where,

P_{ij} selection or choice probability of mode (alternative) j by a person group i .

f Decision function (discrete choice function)

S_i set of characteristics of the person group i , e.g., workers, students etc.

X_j set of characteristics of the alternatives (modes of transport, e.g., car, bike) j , e.g., cost, time etc.

The set of characteristics S_i and X_j (Ben-Akiva & Lerman, 2006)

The set of characteristics, namely S_i and X_j , can be encapsulated under a single terminology commonly known as utility (U). It can be defined as the attractiveness of each alternative that the decision-maker will enjoy if they choose it. A utility has two components, namely:

- Systematic or measured utility, also known as deterministic utility (V).
- Stochastic/random component (ε).

As shown below, the total utility is expressed by adding these two utility types.

$$U = V + \varepsilon \quad (2-3)$$

The deterministic utility (V) contains the explanatory variables that can be measured, e.g., Ride time, fare, and number of transfers. The coefficients (β) or the parameters control the sensitivity of the explanatory variables. A generic utility (deterministic) equation is given below:

$$V_{jq} = \alpha_{jq} + \beta_{j1} \cdot x_{q1} + \beta_{j2} \cdot x_{q2} + \dots = \alpha_{jq} + \sum_k \beta_{jk} \cdot x_{qk} \quad (2-4)$$

$$V_{Students.PT} = 1.0 + (-0.1) \cdot RideTime + (-0.75) \cdot Fare + \dots \quad (2-5)$$

Where,

V_{jq} deterministic utility value

α_{jq} constant for alternative q for group j

β_{jk} parameter determining importance of attribute k for group j

x_{qk} value of attribute k for the alternative q

The decision function f (Ben-Akiva & Lerman, 2006)

The decision function f is also known as the model or choice model class. The type of f depends upon the distribution of the stochastic utility ε , e.g., if the ε is assumed to be independent and identically

distributed as an extreme value distribution $EV(0, \mu)$ (i.i.d. Extreme Value) f is called as logit model. A logit model can be given by:

$$P(i|C_n) = \frac{e^{\mu \cdot V_{in}}}{\sum_{j \in C_n} e^{\mu V_{jn}}} \quad (2-6)$$

where,

C_n a choice set of alternatives with n alternatives

μ scaling factor

V_{in} deterministic utility of alternative i from C_n .

The latent variables (Lee et al., 2003)

Some phenomena cannot be measured; thus, indirect measurements are used to introduce or incorporate them in a choice model. Often, psychometrics is used to solve these problems. An example of indirect measurements of latent concept is, ease of travelling with a particular mode of transport with children. Such variables are called latent variables and are used to explain the utility function. Thus, the intangible perception can be incorporated into the choice modelling framework. These types of choice models are often termed hybrid choice models.

2.2.4 Model testing

The demand models' testing sequence for the PHOEBE use cases is described below:

- **Data collection:** Good data source is the most critical component of the model testing. The data come from the SP/RP surveys and other sources, e.g., census data, land-use data, travel diaries, traffic counts, VehKM, and TripKM data.
- **Model choice:** A suitable choice model will be chosen based on the data collected and the requirements of the use cases.
- **Model estimation:** The input variables and other components of the chosen model will be finalised, and subsequently, the model will be estimated with the data from the surveys and the travel diaries.
- **Model calibration and validation:** The estimated model will then be validated, calibrated, and re-validated with the help of real-world count data. This step will provide a demand model for simulating the current or baseline scenario. This model will produce a baseline mode share, which will be used as a reference to generate the mode shift for the planned scenario.
- **Forecast for the use cases scenarios:** According to the particular use case scenario, the input variables of the baseline demand model will change, producing a forecasted mode share. This mode share will then be compared with the baseline mode share to generate the mode shift for the succeeding processes.

2.3 Traffic microsimulation

Traffic microsimulation in PHOEBE is a key enabler for combining the input from different components of the PHOEBE framework to simulate and forecast the safety impacts of changes and future scenarios across urban transport networks. Testing in a virtual environment speeds up testing, without the delays of real-world implementations and reduce cost, both social and monetary, and to allow reproducibility and control over experiments that would not be possible in the real world.

Microsimulation enables the reproduction of the trajectories of each single road user (pedestrians, bicycles, e-scooters, cars, buses, and others) unveiling their potential unsafe interactions. Leveraging from the power and capabilities of microsimulation to integrate other different models and tools, the PHOEBE framework combines the microsimulation component with mode choice models, human factor

based behavioural models, and road safety assessment models, for reproducing more realistic interactions between different road users and consequently improving the assessment framework for road safety in a prospective manner through giving a methodological framework which can be expanded for the inclusion of emerging and future mobility options.

Traffic microsimulation modelling starts with a transport road graph which involves developing abstract representation of transport networks that consists of links and nodes. These objects have their own attributes that make each of them unique. When multiple links and nodes are linked together, a representation of the mobility network is achieved. The following are the general requirements to build a microsimulation from scratch. This starts with a network representation for the areas to simulate.

A network graph is typically imported from Open Street Map (OSM) and corresponds to 3-dimensional abstract representation of the transport road network. This means having all stationary elements within the road network, enabling the accurate simulation of vehicular movements, such as shown in Figure 2-8 (a).

The network model pertains to the depiction of a network employed by microscopic simulation-driven models. This requires more intricate data, including elements such as traffic management strategies, pedestrian walkways, nodes governed by traffic signals, the type of intersection control, capacities, travel demand, and so forth. An example of a network model is illustrated in Figure 2-8 (b).

Figure 2-8 Network graph vs. network model a) Network graph in OSM b) Network model in Aimsun Next with traffic lights, tramway and bus schedules, priorities at intersections, etc.

After the network is built, the process of calibrating the supply and demand factors is initiated. This is to ensure that the simulation environment represents real traffic conditions and can be used to deploy and

assess the changes, within the PHOEBE Framework. The data which are typically required to perform this task include:

- **Network geometry** – Data describing the geometrical aspects of the use case area.
- **Demand** – Data, expressed in number of trips between origin and destination per transportation mode.
- **Traffic control** – Characterisation of traffic control elements like traffic lights.
- **Transit operation** – Data characterising the operation of public transport, such as transit routes, stops, and schedule.
- **Network traffic state and performance** – Data characterising how traffic behaves along roadway elements, such as volumes, speeds, travel times, location of bottlenecks, etc. Data should be collected for all critical time periods being studied, e.g., AM peak, Midday peak, PM peak, weekend.

2.3.1 Processes

The microsimulation component within the PHOEBE Framework links to other components in the framework, as shown in Figure 2-9 through exchange of several inputs and outputs. To be more specific, the mode choice modelling component provides OD matrices per mode as input to the microsimulation component. It also takes the human factor based behavioural models input from the behavioural modelling component of the framework to represent the driving and walking behaviours of motorised and non-motorised road users in the simulation model. This means that more realistic driving or walking styles are modelled into the microsimulation environment.

With those inputs microsimulation can produce results on variables of interest (KPIs) such as traffic flows per road user type and road segment, travel times, emissions, and many others. The output from microsimulation runs also include individual vehicle / pedestrian trajectories for further processing through a surrogate safety assessment model to identify conflicts, which will be used by the behavioural modelling component for estimating the FSI calibration parameters to be used in the road safety assessment component. In addition, the relevant variables (such as speeds and flows, etc.) from the microsimulation output will also be utilised by the road safety assessment component to calculate the updated risk scores (dynamic) which can then be integrated within the simulation model but only for visualisation purpose.

Figure 2-9 Interaction between traffic microsimulation and other components

2.3.2 Models in traffic simulation

Traffic microsimulation can be overwhelmingly complex and therefore requires a software package that comes with all the necessary features. In general, the models involved are (i) the network representation, which by itself is a model, (ii) the path finding and shortest path models, (iii) demand loading models, (iv) stochastic and random choice models and (v) the models to move vehicles or pedestrians. The last models are the ones to have the greatest impact on safety as they govern the actions of vehicles and pedestrians.

Pedestrians are typically modelled by a social force model. On the other hand, vehicular movements are governed by kinematics models commonly known as vehicle behaviour models within microsimulation modelling domain. For example, typically the vehicles move in the longitudinal axis according to a car-following model, and through the transversal axis according to a lane-changing model. In some occasions, it is possible to have a 2-D model that combines both to have non-lane-based traffic dynamics.

Additionally, there are the gap acceptance models for intersections, which govern the behaviour of vehicles on unsignalised intersections (no traffic lights) and pedestrian decision making at pedestrian crossings. Figure 2-10 illustrates a general modelling flow of traffic microsimulation along with an external control.

Figure 2-10 General modelling flow of traffic microsimulation enabling external control

Within the context of PHOEBE project, which in addition to combining other models and tools within the framework also involves incorporating human factor based behavioural models in microsimulation models, some external application programming interfaces (APIs) will be used as per the needs, for instance, to reflect the drivers' characteristics (such age group, gender etc.) and speeding behaviour, based on the human factor based behavioural models (as explained in section 2.4) on a segment in the model. Similar approach will be applied for modelling the unsafe and/or non-complying behaviours of motorised and non-motorised road users, prioritised within the PHOEBE project.

2.3.3 Data

Traffic microsimulation can generate vast amounts of data, as data can be gathered for each single simulated object at each simulation step. Typically to avoid being overwhelmed with such vast quantities of data, aggregated KPIs are stored and shown to the end user.

2.3.3.1 Aggregated data

At each defined time interval, typically 10 to 15 minutes, aggregated values for the objects of interest are computed and stored for the user. Typical variables are average flow, average speed and average density in the period, vehicular counts (at a location in the network model), vehicles waiting to enter the link, standard deviation of the speed and many others.

Further statistics are gathered to be shown at the end of the simulation as network totals, such as the total vehicles that have travelled through the network, the total delay for all vehicles and per vehicle type, total distance travelled, etc. In some software packages, if the information of the vehicle fleet is given to the simulator, it is possible to obtain the expected air pollutant emissions.

Some software also comes with extension tools that enable to define custom variables and set the logic to compute them in simulation time or load them from external files.

2.3.3.2 Trajectory data

There is the option to store the position of all moving objects (vehicles and pedestrians) for all simulation steps into a database. This kind of data enables the analysis of surrogate safety measures as described in the state of the art and end users needs review ([Section 3.1.7.1 of Deliverable D1.1](#)), making it a useful tool with which to assess the level of risk under different situations.

2.3.3.3 Custom data

It is typically possible with some coding to gather custom information from the simulation, if the variables to compute such data are available within the simulation. This gathered data then must be stored either within the simulation or externally. Leveraging from this capability, and as per the needs of PHOEBE project, the necessary extraction of data from simulation can be done.

2.3.4 Model testing

The accuracy of traffic microsimulation model outcomes is intricately linked to the precision of its calibration. A pertinent challenge in this context revolves around identifying the most impactful input parameters for the (kinematics based) behavioural models (within the simulation software) and macroscopic traffic variables, including variables like traffic flow, speed, and travel time.

Model calibration involves adjusting model parameters and inputs to improve the traffic network model's ability to replicate real traffic conditions. Observed and collected traffic datasets that are statistically significant and provide good coverage of the use cases area are a prerequisite for the calibration process.

Calibration data should include data on road capacity, traffic counts, observations of system performance such as travel times, speeds, delays, and queues, and to some extent travel demand. As a result, a traffic network model calibrated and validated against various traffic data, not only traffic counts, will ensure high predictive ability as it replicates congestion, route choice decisions and travel times in the network to an acceptable level.

In turn, the interactions between road users and their trajectories will be more realistic and accurate to be further used for safety evaluations (baseline vs. future scenarios) and socioeconomic analysis within the PHOEBE framework. Figure 2-11 provides an overview of the model testing steps within microsimulation in, in the context of PHOEBE framework.

Figure 2-11 Model testing process within the Microsimulation Component

2.4 Behavioural models

Behavioural models in PHOEBE aim to incorporate human factors and road user behaviour into traffic microsimulation and road safety assessment. Based on the literature review and the stakeholders needs statement (Section 4.3 of deliverable D1.1), the following human factors are prioritised in PHOEBE:

- Speeding;
- Compliance (red-light running, jaywalking, bicycle path violation, etc.); and
- Aggressiveness.

2.4.1 Processes

The processes that link the behavioural data with the models, and with the other components in PHOEBE are shown in Figures 2-12 and 2-13 below. From the theoretical perspective, there are two direct interactions between behavioural models and other components in PHOEBE:

- The interaction between behavioural models and traffic microsimulation; and
- The interaction between behavioural models and road safety assessment.

On the process side, incorporation of behavioural models in PHOEBE starts with the interaction between behavioural models and traffic microsimulation. As shown in Figure 2-12, empirical data from the use cases will be given to analytical models of road user behaviour (e.g., discrete choice model of speeding) and the outcome probabilities of the target behaviours will be given to traffic microsimulation. These probabilities can be viewed as adjustment factors that need to be used (e.g., multiplied) by the default parameters in traffic microsimulation. After doing so, the microsimulation needs to re-run so that the simulated agents (drivers, pedestrians, cyclists, e-scooters, etc.) behave according to the relevant behavioural models.

Figure 2-12 The interaction process between behavioural models and traffic microsimulation

After re-running the traffic microsimulation, certain traffic characteristics will be extracted including surrogate safety measures (SSM). Simulated speeding behaviours will be extracted too. This simulated data is then used in another set of analytical models of behaviours (e.g., Bayesian discrete choice models) to calculate the probability of traffic conflicts caused by those behaviours.

In parallel, the relationship between observed crashes and simulated conflicts will be developed using Extreme Value Theory (EVT) models. Bringing together the output of Bayesian discrete choice models (i.e., the probability of conflicts by a particular behaviour) and EVT models (i.e., the relationship between conflicts and crashes), the number of crashes per target behaviour is then determined. This final output will be given to road safety assessment as a calibration factor to inform FSI Estimations (Figure 2-13). This whole process (both the first and the second interactions) will be repeated after implementing any scenarios in an iterative manner.

Figure 2-13 The interaction process between behavioural models and road safety assessment

2.4.2 Data

The primary input data for modelling the selected human factors are:

- Individual driving instances with speed over the speed limit or the proportion of vehicular traffic going over the speed limit;
- Individual instances of (lack of) compliance with road rules or the proportion of the same behaviour over the entire traffic; and
- Individual instances of aggressive mobility on the roads or the ratio of the same behaviour over kilometres travelled.

New data collection technologies such as smartphones, cameras, sensors, floating car data and telematics may be used to collect these data.

The behavioural data coming from the above sources relate to actual behaviours. Survey questionnaire data about the prioritised behaviours may also be used as the history (or general trend) of those behaviours. Questions such as: “*In the past two years, how frequently did you cross the street where crossing was not permitted?*” can reflect on the general trend of compliance among a sample of pedestrians in a road network.

In addition to the behavioural data, engineering data, traffic enforcement and road regulations are also other inputs for behavioural models. The physical design of a road infrastructure, the speed distribution of vehicles and other factors such as traffic signals may influence pedestrian behaviour and thus it is important to use these data into behavioural modelling. These data include (but are not limited to) roadway geometry (e.g., intersection type, road width, presence of divided median, horizontal alignment, etc.), traffic composition (e.g., Average Annual Daily Traffic, heavy vehicle, bicycle, e-scooter and pedestrian flows), traffic kinematics (e.g. speed distribution, acceleration, etc.), traffic signals (frequency and duration of traffic signals).

Finally, the risk perception of road users at certain locations may influence their behaviour too and thus may be used in behavioural modelling. For example, drivers may drive more cautiously if they are aware that a certain location in a network is risky. However, risk perception and road user behaviour are endogenous (i.e., they are inter-related). In the above example, driving more cautiously is indeed a risk compensating behaviour. Nevertheless, objective safety and perceived safety are always correlated and hence any information about perceived safety coming from survey questionnaires or even star ratings from existing road safety assessments may be used as a proxy of risk perception in behavioural modelling.

The output data from behavioural models is the probability of an individual or the proportion of the population displaying a certain behaviour. The product of these probabilities will be used to calibrate the FSI Estimation model to determine the number of FSI conflicts caused by the targeted behaviours.

2.4.3 Models

In terms of analytical models for the above human behaviours, **discrete choice models**, **structural equation models**, and potentially the models which account for traffic agents' interdependencies (e.g., **game theoretical models**) can be considered. The first two are the major modelling techniques that have been used in the behavioural science literature to model human behaviour (Bierlaire, 1998; Ullman et al., 2012). The former take the perspective of discrete decision making processes (e.g. discrete instances of going over the speed limit) while the latter looks at the continuous proportions of behaviours over a certain period of time (the ratio of aggressive mobility over kilometres travelled). Game theoretic models offer valuable insights and strategies for addressing road user interactions. These models analyse the behaviour of various participants in traffic scenarios and propose optimal decisions for each party, contributing to the resolution of such interactions (Novikov et al., 2018).

Discrete choice models describe the probability of a certain behaviour as a function of one or more exogenous covariates. Multinomial logit and ordered probit models are two common discrete choice models. The multinomial logit model is used for behaviours that are nominal (do not have order) such as illegal crossing:

$$P(\text{behaviour}) = \frac{\exp(\beta X)}{1 + \exp(\beta X)} \quad (2-7)$$

where X are the exogenous covariates and β are the model parameters.

The ordered probit model is used when the behaviour is ordered such as speeding (low, medium and high severity of speeding):

$$P(s - \text{level of behaviour}) = \varphi\{\tau^{(s+1)} - (\beta X)\} - \varphi\{\tau^{(s)} - (\beta X)\} \quad (2-8)$$

where $\varphi\{\}$ is the cumulative probability distribution function of the normal distribution, τ are model thresholds and the rest of notations are as previously stated.

Structural equation models (SEM), on the other hand, describe the rate of a certain behaviour over a certain period or distance. These models have two components: a measurement model and a structural model. The measurement model is used to determine how well various observable exogenous variables can measure (i.e., load on) the latent variables, as well as the related measurement errors.

The structural model is used to explore how the model variables are interrelated, allowing for both direct and indirect relationships to be modelled. In this sense, SEMs differ from ordinary regression techniques in which relationships between variables are direct. The general formulation of SEM is as follows (Washington et al., 2020):

$$\eta = \beta\eta + \gamma\xi + \varepsilon \quad (2-9)$$

where η is a vector of endogenous variables, ξ is a vector of exogenous variables, β and γ are vectors of coefficients to be estimated, and ε is a vector of regression errors.

The measurement models are then as follows (Chen, 2007):

$$x = \Lambda\xi + \delta, \quad \text{for the exogenous variables}$$

$$y = \Lambda\eta + \zeta, \quad \text{for the endogenous variables}$$

where x and δ are vectors related to the observed exogenous variables and their errors, y and ζ are vectors related to the observed endogenous variables and their errors, and Λ_x , Λ_y are structural coefficient matrices for the effects of the latent exogenous and endogenous variables on the observed variables.

The structural model is often represented by a path analysis, showing how a set of 'explanatory' variables can influence a 'dependent' variable. The paths can be drawn to reflect whether the explanatory variables are correlated causes, mediated causes, or independent causes to the dependent variable.

2.4.4 Model testing

The analytical models for road users' behaviour (equations 1, 2, and 3) need to be empirically tested (estimated or calibrated) for specific datasets from the use cases. To do so, specific behaviours will be selected in each use case to be implemented in PHOEBE. These behaviours will be:

- Athens: (i) speeding behaviour of drivers and (ii) illegal crossing of pedestrians;

- Valencia: (i) illegal crossing of drivers and cyclists (e-scooters) at traffic signals and (ii) illegal crossing of cyclists (e-scooters) in front of trams; and
- West Midlands: (i) speeding behaviour of drivers and (ii) distracted driving.

While aggressiveness is not directly selected to be implemented in the use cases, it will still be studied in all use cases and will be explored as an artefact of the traffic characteristics. Nonetheless, data for all of the above behaviours will be collected in each use case. This data will be used as the dependent variables in the above analytical models. Additional data will also be collected (more on this will be presented in Section 4 of this deliverable) from various sources including crash records, weather stations, survey data, and traffic counts and will be used as independent variables in the models. The models will then be estimated, and the exact parameters and relationships will be determined for each use case.

2.5 Road safety assessment

2.5.1 Data

The iRAP safety Star Rating and the FSI Estimation models are the road safety assessment methodologies applied in PHOEBE. Star Ratings are for assessing risk for an individual road user (for vehicle occupants, motorcyclists, bicyclists and pedestrians) while FSI Estimation models assess collective risk for all road users and road user groups.

The models rely on three primary data sources as input to generate the level of risk in each of the road segments assessed. They are:

- Road-related features, including location information and the physical characteristics of the road and its surrounds. Traditionally, this data is extracted from video or still imagery collected in road surveys for every 100m segments of the network assessed.
- Operational parameters, such as traffic speeds and flows, which are typically supplied by the road authority or collected via traffic counts and speed surveys at set intervals along the road (usually to a minimum of 400m intervals).
- Crash data, which are used to calibrate the FSI Estimation model. It is typically available from a national crash database, but estimations based on alternative sources may be used (e.g. WHO, hospital data).

The road-related features and operational parameters are assigned a numeric value in a specified .CSV file format (a process called “coding”) which is then used by the model to calculate the Star Ratings and FSI Estimations. More information on the categories and coding process and specifications is described in the [iRAP Coding Manual](#).

2.5.1.1 Road-related features

As road safety assessment is an evaluation of the inherent risk and role of infrastructure in the likelihood and severity outcome of crashes, its primary indicators are characteristics of the road environment. For the Star Rating and FSI Estimation models, data on the road-related features (called “attributes”) are divided into seven sub-categories:

- 1 Road details and context: All the necessary information to identify the road segment is required, such as road name, section name, distance (relative km), and length of the section, coordinates and carriageway type. The standard input file for the iRAP models also requires information about the person responsible for inputting the data into the upload file. It requires the coding name, coding date, survey date and the reference of the image that was the base for identifying the attributes.

- 2 Observed flows: Motorcycles, bicycles and pedestrians along or crossing observed flows are part of this group. Observed flows are not directly used in Star Ratings. They are used to validate and check road user flow data.
- 3 Speed limit: Speed limit is collected for general traffic. The speed limit for motorcycles and heavy vehicles may also be collected, but these are used for analytical purposes only (and are not automatically used for Star Rating calculations). Major differences in operating speed or speed limit are recorded, as well as speed management and traffic calming features.
- 4 Mid-block attributes: Road feature attributes that do not relate to intersections. Includes information about the number of lanes, lane width, curvature (radio and quality), median type, grade, sight distance, presence of lighting and delineation must be recorded. Also includes pavement quality attributes (skid resistance and road condition) as well as the presence of vehicle parking, service roads, and road works along the section. These attributes can be correlated with links in the traffic simulation types of networks. Upgrade costs are also collected to support safer road investment plans (i.e., it is not required for Star Ratings or FSI Estimation models).
- 5 Roadside attributes: Roadside objects and their distance from the road. Includes road shoulder width and if there are rumble stripes present in the edge lines.
- 6 Intersection attributes: Features related to intersections, such intersection type (including number of legs, signalisation, turning lanes), intersection quality, connecting road flows, and presence of channelisation and property accesses.
- 7 VRU features: Features related to pedestrians, bicyclists and motorcyclists, such as sidewalks, bicycle and motorcycle facilities, and road crossings and school zones. Includes area type which influences risk factors and land use which is used to help predict the presence of VRUs.

2.5.1.2 Operational parameters

The operation parameters refer to speed and flows of the different road users. This includes vehicle average annual daily traffic (AADT) flow, percentage of motorcycles, pedestrian and bicycle peak hour flows, and operating speeds (85th percentile and mean). More information on the operation parameters can be found in the [iRAP Star Rating and Investment Plan Manual](#).

Speeds

Speed is an essential attribute within the iRAP protocols. The iRAP Star Rating models use the 85th percentile operating speed and speed limit for determining Star Ratings, while mean operating speed is used to generate FSI Estimations.

Traditionally, Star Ratings are based on the larger of the speed limit and the operating speed (85th percentile speed - the speed at or below which 85 percent of all vehicles are observed to travel under free-flowing conditions past a monitored point). The model enhancement as part of PHOEBE will prioritise the operating speeds to allow speed fluctuation along the day.

Speed risk factors also inform countermeasure triggers and economic benefits. The speed risk factors work as multipliers for every crash type included in the model, highly impacting the Star Rating Score.

Flows

The Star Rating models use different flow parameters. They are:

Vehicles flows: Vehicle flows are represented by the Annual average daily traffic (AADT). The AADT is used in the calculation of Star Ratings and to estimate the number of fatalities for each 100m segment of road. Higher traffic flows increase a road user's exposure to certain crash types, such as a head-on

collision. Generally, a larger AADT will result in a lower Star Rating and a higher estimated number of fatalities for a 100m segment of road. Motorcyclists and heavy vehicles are counted as the percentage of those types of vehicles in the daily flows. A motorcyclist Star Rating will only be calculated if motorcyclists are present. If the motorcycle % is zero, then no motorcyclist Star Rating will be produced and the estimate of motorcyclist fatalities will be zero.

Bicyclists flow: Considers all bicycles, including conventional bicycles and e-bikes, passing through the segment in the peak hour. Bicycle flow is used to estimate the number of bicyclist fatalities for each 100m segment of road. A bicyclist Star Rating will only be calculated if bicyclists are present. If the bicyclist peak hour flow is zero, then no bicyclist Star Rating will be produced, and the estimate of bicyclist fatalities will be zero. Ideally this data will be supplied by the road authority or other relevant organisation. In circumstances where reliable flow data are not available estimates must be made. The process for estimating bicycle flows should follow a similar methodology as for pedestrian flows.

Pedestrian flows: Pedestrian peak hour flows are recorded individually for flows along the driver-side, along the passenger-side and across the road. Changes in pedestrian flows do not affect the Star Ratings, though larger pedestrian flows will result in a lower and higher estimated number of pedestrian fatalities. If pedestrian flow across and along the road is zero, then no corresponding Star Rating will be produced and the estimate of pedestrian fatalities will be zero. Ideally, this data will be supplied by the road authority. In circumstances where reliable flow data is not available, estimates must be made. The final peak hour pedestrian flows used in the analysis ultimately need to reflect the specific road environment. Relationships between flows and road attributes can vary significantly between countries and regions. It is therefore good practice to develop a methodology for estimating flows that reflects the specific context of the assessment.

2.5.1.3 Crash data

Numbers of fatalities by road user and crash type are used to calibrate the dataset and produce the FSI Estimation and Investment Plan reports in ViDA (The iRAP computational platform for star rating and FSI estimation models). Calibration factors are used to ensure that the total estimated number of FSI on the network is equal to the actual number of FSI on that network.

Ideally, crash data for a 3-year period will be supplied by the road authority or another relevant agency, such as police. The fatalities must be distributed into user groups and crash types and inputted as number of fatalities or percentages of the total fatalities. Table 2-2 displays the user groups and the types of crashes for which the information is needed.

Table 2-2 User groups and crash types in question

User groups	Crash types
Car occupants	Run-off LOC driver-side
Motorcyclists	Run-off LOC passenger-side
Pedestrians	Head-on LOC
Bicyclists	Head-on overtaking
Micro mobility (e.g. e-scooters)	Intersection
	Property access
	Along
	Crossing intersected road
	Crossing inspected road
	Other

*LOC: Loss of Control

The CycleRAP model will also be used in selected use cases where cyclists and other Light Mobility Vehicle (LMV) users are the primary focus. The data collected for CycleRAP is different to that described above since the assessments are centered on facilities bicyclists and LMV are using which may not necessarily capture from the road network as is in the Star Rating models.² However, the two may be used together. Details and specifications for the CycleRAP data can be found at the [CycleRAP User Guide](#).

The output data the Star Rating and FSI Estimation models includes:

- Crash type scores per road user group (vehicle occupant, pedestrian, bicyclist, motorcyclist);
- Star Rating Scores (SRS) and Star Ratings per road user group;
- FSI Estimations per road user group and for all road users; and
- For CycleRAP, risk scores by crash type (vehicle-bicycle/LMV; bicycle/LMV- bicycle/LMV; bicycle/LMV-pedestrian; single bicycle/LMV) and total risk score (combined).

The full list of Star Rating and FSI Estimation output data is provided in Table 2-3.

Table 2-3 Star Rating and FSI Estimations model output data

Users	Risk Scores	Fatality estimations	Star Ratings
Vehicle occupants	Vehicle SRS Run-Off LOC Driver-Side	Vehicle Occupant FSI Estimation Run-Off LOC Driver-side per km per year	Vehicle Star Rating Raw
	Vehicle SRS Run-Off LOC Passenger-Side	Vehicle Occupant FSI Estimation Run-Off LOC Passenger-side per km per year	Vehicle Star Rating Smoothed
	Vehicle SRS Head-On LOC	Vehicle Occupant FSI Estimation Head-On LOC per km per year	
	Vehicle SRS Head-On Overtaking	Vehicle Occupant FSI Estimation Head-On Overtaking per km per year	
	Vehicle SRS Intersection	Vehicle Occupant FSI Estimation Intersection per km per year	
	Vehicle SRS Property Access	Vehicle Occupant FSI Estimation Property Access per km per year	
	Vehicle SRS Total	Vehicle Occupant FSI Estimation Total per km per year	
	Vehicle SRS Total Smoothed		
Motorcyclists	Motorcyclist SRS Run-Off LOC Driver-Side	Motorcyclist FSI Estimation Run-Off LOC Driver-side per km per year	Motorcyclist Star Rating Raw
	Motorcyclist SRS Run-Off Passenger-Side	Motorcyclist FSI Estimation Run-Off LOC Passenger-side per km per year	Motorcyclist Star Rating Smoothed
	Motorcyclist SRS Head-On LOC	Motorcyclist FSI Estimation Head-On LOC per km per year	

² Like Star Rating data, CycleRAP data includes facility-related attributes and operational attributes.

Users	Risk Scores	Fatality estimations	Star Ratings
Motorcyclists (cont.)	Motorcyclist SRS Head-On Overtaking	Motorcyclist FSI Estimation Head-On Overtaking per km per year	
	Motorcyclist SRS Intersection	Motorcyclist FSI Estimation Intersection per km per year	
	Motorcyclist SRS Property-Access	Motorcyclist FSI Estimation Property Access per km per year	
	Motorcyclist SRS Along	Motorcyclist FSI Estimation Along per km per year	
	Motorcyclist SRS Total	Motorcyclist FSI Estimation Total per km per year	
	Motorcyclist SRS Total Smoothed	Motorcyclist FSI Estimation Total per km per year	
Pedestrians	Pedestrian SRS Along	Pedestrian FSI Estimation Along Driver-side per km per year	Pedestrian Star Rating Raw
	Pedestrian SRS Crossing Intersecting Road	Pedestrian FSI Estimation Along Passenger-side per km per year	Pedestrian Star Rating Smoothed
	Pedestrian SRS Crossing Inspected Road	Pedestrian FSI Estimation Crossing Side Road per km per year	
	Pedestrian SRS Total	Pedestrian FSI Estimation Crossing Through Road per km per year	
	Pedestrian SRS Total Smoothed	Pedestrian FSI Estimation Total per km per year	
Bicyclists	Bicyclist SRS Along	Bicyclist FSI Estimation Along per km per year	Bicyclist Star Rating Raw
	Bicyclist SRS Intersection	Bicyclist FSI Estimation Intersection per km per year	Bicyclist Star Rating Smoothed
	Bicyclist SRS Run-Off	Bicyclist FSI Estimation Run-Off per km per year	
	Bicyclist SRS Total	Bicyclist FSI Estimation Total per km per year	
	Bicyclist SRS Total Smoothed	Bicyclist FSI Estimation Total per km per year	

**LOC: Loss of Control
SRS: Star Rating Scores

2.5.2 Models and processes

The Star Rating and FSI Estimation model use an evidence-based, standardised approach. This allows reliability and transferability of the PHOEBE structure to other cities. The first deliverable in PHOEBE (D1.1 State of the art and end-users need) described how the Star Rating, CycleRAP and the FSI Estimations models work and its characteristics that are advantageous to a road safety framework.

As part of the PHOEBE Framework, the Star Ratings and the CycleRAP models bring the infrastructure risk component to measure road safety impact. Star Ratings represent a risk to an individual user type (vehicle occupant, motorcyclist, bicyclist, and pedestrian) and is the sum of individual crash type scores

(run-off-road, heads-on, intersections and access points, travelling along the road and crossing the road). They are an objective measure of:

- i. How likely it is that a road crash will occur for an individual road user, based on the speed, volume and physical features of the road; and
- ii. The severity of the outcome when a crash does occur.

The iRAP models consider the contribution of several infrastructure and operational elements described in the previous section and their contribution to one or both previously discussed components. They are combined in a multiplicative model to determine total risk, associated Star Rating, and FSI Estimations.

While the Star Rating model indicates the risk to an individual road user, the FSI Estimation Model considers the Star Rating results to estimate how many FSI crashes will occur on the road network, considering exposure (road user flows). Therefore, the FSIs will be the main indicator of safety for the PHOEBE framework.

Figure 2-14 Road Safety assessment process flow within PHOEBE framework

The road safety assessment process is detailed in Figure 2-14. From the theoretical perspective, road safety assessment (that is, the Star Ratings, FSI Estimations and where relevant, CycleRAP) interact with the other elements within the PHOEBE Framework in five different stages of the process.

From road safety assessment to other components:

- i. Static risk scores are inputs for demand and behavioural models;
- ii. Dynamic risks scores are an input for traffic simulation, however, only for visualisation; and
- iii. Crash risk scores and FSIs are used to generate PHOEBE KPIs.

From other components to road safety assessment:

- i. Dynamic risk scores which use variable speed and flow data from traffic simulation; and
- ii. Behavioural calibration factors for the FSI Estimation model.

The road safety assessment flow can start in two different ways depending on whether the assessments already exist or if it is an entirely new assessment. Both result in 'static' scores, that is, a risk score for a point in time.

For new assessments, the process starts with data gathering (road survey and/or data gathering from AI and other sources). A comprehensive dataset is compiled which align with that described in [section 2.5.1](#). The collected data is then used to calculate the preliminary crash scores for each individual road segment.

Where there is an existing assessment (and therefore pre-existing data as well as output data in the form of Star Ratings and FSI Estimations), the process starts with converting the 100-segment results to be compatible with the simulation network (links and nodes). Existing or new datasets then serve as the foundation for the baseline assessment phase.

Explainer notes

Changing the data structure to reflect nodes and links

The Star Rating Score (SRS) and the FSI Estimation are calculated for each 100m road segment for vehicle occupants, motorcyclists, pedestrians and bicyclists. This means that all road attribute data comprises 100m coding segments.

The 100m segments are equally distributed from the assessment's starting point defined by the survey. When a new survey starts, a new reference starting point is established. Each row of the ViDA core files represents one 100m segment. The latitudes and longitudes provided refer to the beginning of each segment.

However, simulation models structure the data differently: using nodes and links. Three approaches will be developed and tested for PHOEBE:

(i) Procedure for networks with most links with more than 100m

When most of the links in the network are more than 100m long, the data coding can still be done per 100m segment, and the data point will be spatially joined by the link, with the risk score averaged by the link and the FSI's summed. Procedures to compatibilise the networks will be established and tested during WP3.

(ii) Procedure for networks with most links with less than 100m

When most of the links in the network are less than 100m long, coding needs to be done per link. The impacts of changing the coding standardisation will be tested and analysed as part of WP3 using PHOEBE use cases.

(iii) Procedure to match intersection scores and nodes

Intersections, particularly in cities and urban areas, can take many forms. In reality, intersections may have as many as 6- or 8-legs and be a combination of slip lanes, on and off ramps to overpasses, and

staged traffic signals. Therefore, matching Star Rating data points that present an intersection coded with micro-simulation nodes is far more complex than matching mid-block sections with links. Due to the complexity described above, the PHOEBE framework will provide guidelines on matching intersection scores and nodes per intersection type. The intersections in the use case study areas offer many examples, including 3 and 4-leg junctions, roundabouts and merge lanes in single or double-carriageways.

User guidelines on how to identify the best procedure and how to operate the analysis will be developed as part of WP3.

After the static results are generated and structured according to links and nodes, the Star Rating models wait for output data (variable speed and flows) from the traffic microsimulation and the FSI calibration parameters received from the behavioural modelling component. These are then used to generate the 'dynamic' risk profiles. The dynamic crash scores are then sent back to the traffic simulation tool for visualisation purposes and will be used to inform PHOEBE KPIs. Visual maps are then used to illustrate the spatial distribution of risk scores across the entire expanse of the road network.

Star Ratings will be recalculated in step 2, to take into account changes in road conditions, speeds and road user flows.

2.5.2.1 Estimating FSI

Estimating FSI uses the iRAP FSI Estimation model to predict the number of FSI associated with each specific road segment over a given period (typically 20 years). The process relies on a comprehensive understanding of the road attributes in conjunction with their interaction with the prevailing traffic conditions. The FSI Estimation model will generate the first estimates based on the infrastructure crash risk (the Star Ratings), number of road users and is calibrated using crash data (for the baseline scenario).³ Variable speed and flow data from the traffic microsimulation and behavioural calibration factors Estimates from behaviour models will adjust these values. The final FSIs will inform PHOEBE KPIs and socio-economic analysis.

FSI Estimations will be recalculated in step 2 based on changes in the Star Rating, road user flows and behaviour calibration factors. This allows provides the basis to understand the safety impacts of the changes.

Explainer notes

Variable speed and flows to produce dynamic risk scores

The Star Ratings, CycleRAP, and FSI estimations models provide a static risk evaluation. This means the results refer to a specific time-related point related to the moment the images were captured and the supporting data collected.

Traffic speeds and flows are highly variable compared to infrastructure-related elements of a road. With new technologies capture data much faster, the risk assessment model can capture these variations and provide dynamic risk scores. This helps road authorities understand changes that may be occurring throughout a typical day, and address times when risk is highest.

The dynamic allocation of speed and flows requires enhancements in the current models. The following enhancements are planned in WP3:

³ This calibration takes into account factors which are beyond those considered by the Star Rating models, such as vehicle safety standards and features (e.g. seat belts and airbags), road user behaviours (aside from operating speed which is directly considered) and crash response which may influence FSI outcomes.

Establishment of the database structure to account for more than one risk result per location: to allow risk calculation, for instance, for different hours of the day, the model input file needs to be structured in a way that would enable computation and visualisation of the results.

Methodology for non-daily flows: Currently, the model uses Road AADT for vehicles and motorcycle flows and peak hour flows for bicycles and pedestrians. The model needs to be prepared and tested to receive inputs of different parameters for vehicle and VRU flows.

Data transferability procedures to automate risk calculation based on traffic simulation inputs: Standardisations of inputs/outputs formats and the API connections need to be developed together with the traffic simulation tool to allow smooth data sharing among models.

Calibration of FSI to reflect behavioural changes

The FSI Estimation model is calibrated using crash data for the assessed roads. The calibration factors (CF) check that the total estimated number of FSI on the network is equal to the actual number of FSI on that network. The following equations show the CF formula for the pedestrian crash crossing the inspected road (PED CR-IR) crash fatalities as an example:

$$CF_{PED\ CR-IR} = \frac{\text{Actual no. of pedestrian crash fatalities when crossing the inspected road on the network}}{\sum(SRS_{PED-CR-IR} \times a(AADT)^b \times VNON-MC \times FG)} \quad (2-12)$$

where,

$CF_{PED\ CR-IR}$ = Calibration factor for pedestrian crash fatalities when crossing the inspected road

n = the number of 100-metre segments of road

$SRS_{PED-CR-IR}$ = Star Rating Score for pedestrians crossing the inspected road

a = AADT multiplier

AADT = annual average daily traffic

b = AADT power

V NON-MC = non-motorcycle AADT

FG = fatality growth exponent

In this way, the FSI Estimation model takes account of factors that influence the number of fatalities on the road other than infrastructure, speed and flow. Therefore, when crash data is available, the FSIs account for FSI originating from unsafe behaviour. FSIs will be calibrated based on the behavioural model results. The proposition is that the calibration factor formula will have an extra component representing the percentage of increase/decrease in the number of deaths for the particular behaviour studied and provide more granularity in the calibration. The approach and testing will be finalised in the WP3 activities.

2.5.3 Model testing

All planned enhancements to the models will be tested. The iRAP ViDA system provides access to testing data in more than 90 countries, ensuring that training and testing phases encompass a diverse range of diverse traffic scenarios. This rigorous analysis of all the methods not only substantiates its effectiveness within the PHOEBE project but also showcases its potential for enhancing road safety on a broader scale.

2.6 Safety indicators and dynamic risk outputs

The basic definition of risk in safety science is the occurrence probability of an event multiplied by the consequence of that event. Based on this definition, many indicators can be defined for risk and safety on the road.

Traditionally, road crashes are used as indicators of road safety (in which the risk can be calculated as the probability of crash occurrence multiplied by the severity of crashes). However, there are many issues

with using crashes as an indicator. First it is a reactive approach, meaning one or more people need to be involved in FSI crashes before safety issues are noticed or addressed; and second, many crashes (particularly the property damage only crashes) are not reported and so their data are not available in the crash databases. This is particularly the case for non-vehicle occupant road users.

However, predictive models can identify zones at high risk of FSI crashes with an acceptable level of confidence. From many years of research in road safety, it is already well-known what road components affect the likelihood and severity of crashes. Many prediction formulations have been established and used as presented in D1.1.

Recently, surrogate safety measures have been commonly used for road safety assessment (as explained in section 3.1.7.1 of D1.1), to identify traffic conflicts by processing the vehicular trajectories from the output of traffic microsimulations. Traffic conflicts have been used more recently as proactive and more frequent indicators of safety (in which case the risk would be the probability of conflicts multiplied by their severity).

According to the Swedish Traffic Conflicts Technique, the same causes can be attributed to near-crashes or traffic conflicts and can act as a tool for safety assessment. The various possible interactions between road users and the associated risk can be further elaborated through the “safety pyramid” by Hydén (Figure 2-15; Hydén, 1987), presenting different zones of safety critical events while also reflecting the associated severity.

Figure 2-15 Classification of safety critical events according to the Swedish Traffic Conflicts Technique (Hyden, 1987)

The Federal Highway Administration (FHWA)’s Surrogate Safety Assessment Model (SSAM) provides various parameters for identifying the traffic conflicts including:

- TTC = Time to collision;
- PET = Post-encroachment time;
- DR = Deceleration rate;
- MaxS = Maximum of the speeds of two vehicles;
- DeltaS = Maximum relative speed;
- Classification as lane-change, rear-end, or path-crossing event type;
- DeltaV = Vehicle velocity change had the event proceeded to a crash.

In addition to the direct safety measures, there are some factors which are *predictors* of safety (as opposed to direct indicators). For example, harsh acceleration or cornering may directly lead to conflicts or crashes and so they are good predictors of safety. For both indicators and predictors of safety, some are fine-

grained (suitable for microscopic safety analysis), and some are more aggregated (suitable for macroscopic safety); some are only relevant for drivers (e.g., harsh acceleration), and some are relevant for vulnerable road users too (e.g., conflicts). As a result, it is of high importance to create a taxonomy of safety indicators to better integrate the data, models and processes of the components in PHOEBE and establish the methodology.

2.6.1 Taxonomy of safety (risk) indicators

The taxonomy of safety indicators (Table 2-4) is developed considering both indicators and predictors of safety. The indicators include:

- Direct measures such as crashes (number and severity);
- Surrogate measures such as conflicts (frequency and severity);
- Predictor variables such as hazardous factors such as related to infrastructure (from road safety assessment star ratings); and
- Human factors (risky behaviours of road users), which can lead to potential collisions.

Factors associated with crash causes are generally categorised as driver-related, vehicle-related or related to the roadway environment (infrastructure, pavement surface condition, sight obstructions, and others).

The predictor variables include a variety of safety critical factors related to infrastructure and road users' behaviours, which can potentially lead to collisions, such as:

- Inadequacies within the Infrastructure for safe traffic operations;
- Lack of compliance to roadway rules, distracted driving, fatigued driving, aggressive driving behaviours, etc.

Vehicle structural characteristics within various vehicle types are out of the scope and hereby have not been considered.

Table 2-4 Taxonomy of Safety/Risk Indicators

Road Users	Variable	Level	Relationship with Risk
Drivers and vehicle occupants	Conflicts (frequency and severity) (calculated using TTC, PET, DR, MaxS, DeltaS, type, DeltaV)	Micro: Individual instances Meso: Number of conflicts across a segment / at an intersection Macro: Number of conflicts over a network	Indicator
	Crashes (frequency and severity - FSI)	Micro: Individual crashes Meso: Number of crashes across a segment / at an intersection Macro: Number of crashes over a network	Indicator
	Star Rating Risk Scores (Infrastructure)	Meso: risk score of a segment / intersection	Indicator

Road Users	Variable	Level	Relationship with Risk
Drivers and vehicle occupants (cont.)	Aggressive driving (e.g., harsh acceleration, short headway, aggressive lane-change and over taking etc.)	<p>Micro: Individual instances</p> <p>Meso: Number of instances across a segment / at an intersection</p> <p>Macro: Number of instances over a network</p>	Predictor
	Fatigued driving (e.g., reduced attention due to drowsiness)	<p>Micro: Individual instances</p> <p>Meso: Number of instances across a segment / at an intersection</p> <p>Macro: Number of instances over a network</p>	Predictor
	Non-compliance: Red light running Distracted driving (e.g., use of cell phone) Not yielding to other road users with right of way Driving over the speed limit Not using seat belts	<p>Micro: Individual Instances</p> <p>Meso: Number of instances over a segment / at an intersection</p> <p>Macro: Number of instances over a network</p>	Predictor
Pedestrians	Conflicts (frequency and severity) (TTC, PET, DR, MaxS, DeltaS, type, DeltaV)	<p>Micro: Individual instances</p> <p>Meso: Number of conflicts across a segment / at an intersection</p> <p>Macro: Number of conflicts over a network</p>	Indicator
	Crashes (frequency and severity -FSI)	<p>Micro: Individual instances</p> <p>Meso: Number of crashes across a segment / at an intersection</p> <p>Macro: Number of crashes over a network</p>	Indicator
	Star Rating Risk Scores (Infrastructure)	<p>Meso: Star rating risk scores of a segment / intersection</p>	Indicator AND predictor
	Non-compliance: Red-light running J-walking Not walking on the sidewalk	<p>Micro: Individual Instances</p> <p>Meso: Number of instances over a segment / at an intersection</p> <p>Macro: Number of instances over a network</p>	Predictor
Cyclists and LMV	Conflicts (frequency and severity) (TTC, PET, DR, MaxS, DeltaS, type, DeltaV)	<p>Micro: Individual instances</p> <p>Meso: Number of conflicts across a segment / at an intersection</p> <p>Macro: Number of conflicts over a network</p>	Indicator

Road Users	Variable	Level	Relationship with Risk
Cyclists and LMV (cont.)	Crashes (frequency and severity -FSI)	<u>Micro:</u> Individual instances <u>Meso:</u> Number of crashes across a segment / at an intersection <u>Macro:</u> Number of crashes over a network	Indicator
	Star Rating risk scores (Infrastructure)	<u>Meso:</u> Star rating risk scores of a segment / intersection	Indicator AND predictor
	Non-compliance: Red-light running Not using the dedicated path (for cyclists and e-scooters) Not yielding to road users with right of way	<u>Micro:</u> Individual Instances <u>Meso:</u> Number of instances over a segment / at an intersection <u>Macro:</u> Number of instances over a network	Predictor

The variables within the above taxonomy are classified based on road user type (drivers, pedestrians, cyclists, e-scooter users, etc.) at microscopic (individual instances), mesoscopic (across a segment), and macroscopic (over a network) level.

Under drivers' category, a variety of driving related safety critical factors are listed including those related to infrastructure (presented as iRAP Star Ratings) and those related to driving behaviours including aggressive driving such as:

- Maintaining short headway, harsh acceleration, aggressive lane-change or overtaking etc.;
- Fatigued driving such as reduced attention due to tiredness or lack of sleep; or
- Violations of roadway rules such as driving over the speed limit, running the red light, not yielding to road users with right of way etc.

Similarly, under the categories of pedestrians, and cyclists and e-scooter, variables include those related to infrastructure and behaviours. The main behavioural factors are related to non-compliance such as red-light running, illegal crossing, not using a dedicated facility, or not yielding.

The taxonomy of safety indicators and predictors highlights the data needs and underlines the need for coherent interactions between traffic microsimulation and behavioural models and between the behavioural models and road safety assessment, as presented in Figure 2-12 and 2-13 under section 2.4.1.

2.6.2 Risk indicators in traffic microsimulation

Traffic microsimulation is not typically used for risk evaluation. The primary reasons are that the behavioural models used to model traffic flows by a specified set of rules which are engineered to be safe by definition, effectively making it impossible for crashes to occur in the modelled traffic. Crashes in the real world are also infrequent. To get any meaningful crash dataset in a simulation thousands of hours' worth of simulation over large networks would require having enough interaction to gather a statistically significant number of crashes (just like it is in the real world).

Severe traffic conflicts in simulation are known as surrogate safety measures (SSM), to assess safety without the need of having crashes. They are computed by saving the trajectory data of every single vehicle and pedestrian as explained in section 2.2. Aimsun Next can export such data into various formats: SQLite, FZP Exporter and SSAM. The main difference between the formats is how data is formatted, and ease of use for different purposes. In all cases, Aimsun Next has all the information required to assess SSM, including:

- Object ID, to identify each different object in the network;
- ID of the next vehicle downstream (only vehicles);
- Object type;
- Vehicle length (only vehicles);
- Object position in x,y coordinates;
- Simulation time;
- Object speed; and
- Vehicle acceleration (only vehicles).

Since trajectory data has the position, speed and acceleration of all moving objects at all simulation steps, the trajectories can be reconstructed. This means that any SSM can be computed by coding a script that reads the data and computes the desired metrics. If the standard FHWA SSAM package wants to be used, then the SSAM export can be selected and Aimsun Next exports trajectory data in the exact format the SSAM tool requires, needing no extra steps.

The metrics to be used are the ones defined at subsection 2.5.1, these are TTC, PET, DR, MaxS, DeltaV and DeltaS which are described as follows:

- TTC is the time until two moving objects collide if they keep moving at the same speed and direction. Thus, the TTC is the time the two parties with overlapping trajectories on the space time (i.e. collision) have to react and avoid the collision, in this case the lower the value the riskier it is.
- PET quantifies the time between two moving objects are in the same point in space, that is, how much time has passed since object one left the collision zone until the second one enters it. The smaller the time, the higher the risk.
- DR is the maximum negative acceleration rate at which the vehicle reduces its speed, in this case high values imply high risk.
- MaxS is the maximum speed.
- DeltaV is the sudden speed change to if the collision were to happen, and provides an indicator of the conflict severity.
- DeltaS is the maximum relative speed between the two vehicles and/or pedestrians of interest.

All SSM explained can be computed from the trajectory dataset. PET will be computed using the trajectory data x,y positions and the time stamps. TTC will additionally need the speed value. DR only needs the acceleration component of the trajectory dataset. Similarly, MaxS will use the speed component of the trajectory dataset. DeltaV and DeltaS will require the same data as TTC to compute the speed difference between pairs of objects in close proximity, hence the need for the spatial coordinates.

The SSM enhanced by the behavioural inputs in the PHOEBE framework generate safety indicators reflecting the behavioural changes (human behavioural or mode shift). Therefore, the Framework is expected to estimate FSI resulting from the behavioural changes analysed in the simulated scenario. Transforming conflicts into crashes will allow for harmonising the safety indicators with the road safety assessments.

As described in [Section 2.5.2](#), the FSI Estimation model uses the infrastructure elements' risk and the traffic flow exposure to estimate the number of victims in each section of the network assessed. The model uses crash data to calibrate the total number of fatalities, considering, in this way, other phenomena that can be explained purely by the infrastructure influence. By having the same unit of analysis (expected FSI), the PHOEBE Framework creates a standard and harmonised outputs for the PHOEBE models (road safety assessments and behavioural model through the traffic simulation results). Combining the two estimations into one indicator still needs to be elaborated to ensure compatibility. A possible arrangement is the estimations from the behaviour components to work as an adjustment factor to the iRAP FSIs.

2.6.3 Dynamic safety (risk) indicators

Safety indicators based on variable speeds and flows will provide a dynamic risk profile over a given period. The on- and off-peak hours are the starting points, but the simulation can run for different time segments if demand data is available.

Speeds and flows are inputs and outputs for all the components of PHOEBE and can be modelled for different road user groups. Therefore, speeds and flows are key attributes for dynamic modelling of road user risk and scenario testing.

Although the infrastructure elements are less volatile than speeds and flows, analysis of the dynamic allocation of space or impact of infrastructure elements along the day can also be performed. For example, street lighting on cycle paths might attract cyclists to ride at night. The increase in the cyclist volume after 6 p.m. might escalate conflicts at intersections. Therefore, a fixed infrastructure element might present a dynamic influence through safety throughout the day.

Different indicators can evaluate the dynamic risk (Table 2-5). Selection depends on the available data and the number of timeframes modelled since some indicators highly depend on the number of data analysis points.

Table 2-5 Possible indicators to evaluate dynamic risks

Dynamic KPI	Description	Examples
Average distance from the lowest risk data point (per user, per crash type, per link, per node, for the entire network)	Considering that the risk should be as low as possible, the dynamic indicators should indicate how far the other analysis points throughout the day are from the lower risk points regarding risk scores or fatal and severe injury estimations.	Link A presented the calculated risk as 0.020 at the off-peak hour scenario, while the peak scenario risk increased to 0.100. The calculated distance would then be 0.080. After the intervention, the off-peak risk decreased to 0.015 at the off-peak hour scenario, while the peak scenario risk decreased to 0.075. The calculated distance is not 0.06, showing that the intervention reduces the variability of the risk through the day.

Dynamic KPI	Description	Examples
<p>% of the data where speed is above safe speed limits for VRUs in urban areas</p>	<p>The speed itself can be an indicator of risk, especially in urban areas where safe speed limit and speed compliance is key to account for the fragility of vulnerable road users. The indicator should be correlated with other parameters of the network like road hierarchy.</p>	<p>Link B is a local residential road where, in 50% of the data points analysed, vehicles were travelling at more than 20 km/h.</p> <p>After installing traffic calming devices, only 10% of the data points analysed presented vehicles travelling at more than 20 km/h.</p>
<p>% of data points in the simulation period (day, hour) above safe marks (or less than 3 star or better)</p>	<p>Risk can fluctuate on a safe range of values but should stay within the limit where the risk is acceptable.</p> <p>This indicator highlights how many data analysis points in the simulation period are above the limits to prioritise changes.</p>	<p>Node C present the risk above the limit in three different time scenarios (Morning peak, lunch peak, and evening peak) of the 5 data points analysed (60%).</p> <p>After intervention, only morning peak is still ranked with peak hours above the limits, reducing the percentage to 20%.</p>

3 Socioeconomic analysis

Socioeconomic analysis (SEA) is the last component of PHOEBE's methodological framework. A detailed description of this component is presented in Figure 3-1 below. SEA is one of the most critical components as it evaluates the effectiveness and the impacts of road safety measures from social and economic points of view. Initially, Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) and Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA) are chosen to carry out the SEA since these methods encompass detail of cost and benefit considerations and calculations. However, at the later stages of the project, if there arises a requirement for other SEA methodologies, e.g., Multi-Criteria Analysis or Best-Worst Analysis, these analyses can be carried out as extensions of CBA and CEA. As discussed in Section 2.1.3, the computations within the socioeconomic analysis component will incorporate all the possible changes in the costs and benefits occurring with time inherently and/or due to implementation of the proposed short and long-term measures. To carry out the SEA, an array of network-level indicators will be considered. These indicators (Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)) will encompass three principal issues or themes, namely health and safety, environmental and economic.

Table 3-1 (not an exhaustive list), under section 3.2.1.1, presents these KPIs and the principal issues they address. It is to be noted that additional KPIs may be added, and the currently listed KPIs can be edited or removed from the list depending on the detailed modelling considerations.

This component is also distributed in three parts: Procedure (computation), Data (for computation), and Feedback to the preceding components (Updates). Figure 3-1 presents the details of this component.

Figure 3-1 SEA component

3.1 Procedure

This section elaborates on two methods of SEA that are chosen for assessing the socioeconomic impacts of the deployed changes to be considered in PHOEBE. The chosen methods are:

- Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA); and
- Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA).

3.1.1 Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)

CBA is a systematic socioeconomic evaluation technique deployed to evaluate a project, policy, or decision's pros and cons. It is carried out by comparing the total costs associated with implementing the project, policy, or decision to the total benefits generated by it.

Since a deployed change is such an intervention, the CBA can be used to evaluate the social and economic impacts of a particular change. CBA is a quantitative method of evaluation. The primary objective of a cost-benefit analysis is to determine whether the benefits of an action outweigh its costs in monetary terms.

The steps of carrying out a CBA against a change are described below. Figure 3-1 provides a conceptual flow of the process.

- a) **Identifying the benefits:** The benefits of a deployed change chiefly comprise two separate elements (Daniels et al., 2019), namely:
 - I. The number of crashes prevented by the deployed change; and
 - II. Other possible benefits relating to the mobility and environmental impacts.
- b) **Quantifying or monetising the benefits:** Specific benefits generated by any change are quantitative, e.g., property damage avoidance and emergency cost savings. However, part of the benefits are qualitative, e.g., the number of deaths and severe injuries prevented. These KPIs are qualitative because the costs associated with these KPIs are variable and depend upon several factors. To estimate the costs associated with such KPIs, a technique like Willingness-to-Pay (WTP) is deployed.
 - Willingness-to-Pay method: The following scenario is considered to describe the WTP method. Suppose a change or policy is expected to reduce the number of deaths caused by road crashes n by over a given time frame for a population of size P . Now, if v is the average amount each member of the population is willing to pay to fund the road safety measure for risk reduction, then the total amount to be paid by the population is $v \cdot P$. Thus, the willingness to pay per fatality is $(v \cdot P)/n$ (OECD, 2001). WTP can be further used to estimate the Value of Statistical Life (VoSL) or the Value of Preventing a Fatality (VPF). VoSL, or VPF, is a quantitative (often monetary) value used to quantify the benefit of avoiding a fatality. Generally, empirical approaches, e.g., Revealed (OECD, 2001) or Stated preference methods (contingent valuation) (Antoniou, 2014; Rizzi & Ortúzar, 2006), are deployed to estimate WTP and VoSL.
 - Stated preference (SP) method: This method is dependent on stated preference surveys (Antoniou, 2014). The respondents are asked to deliver their responses through a rating scale. A suitable discrete choice model (e.g., Multinomial or Nested logit (in case the IIA does not hold)) is then selected, with each potential response coded as an alternative. An example of the SP method with ordered probit model is presented below. Suppose Y is the response variable with K levels (scales); in this case the model can be represented as (Antoniou, 2014):

$$P(x) = \Phi(\theta_j - \beta'x) \quad (3-1)$$

where,

Φ is the cumulative normal function

$\theta_0 = -\infty < \theta_1 < \dots < \theta_k < \infty$ are the break points

x is the vector of explanatory variables

β is the vector of unknown parameters

The distribution of the choice probability P as the function of the utility U can be presented as Figure 3-2.

The road safety benefits for a period n , depending on level of severity s that results from the introduction of a measure, can then be calculated as (Daniels et al., 2019):

$$Benefits_n = \sum_n Targetcrashes_s * Effectiveness_s * Crashcost_s \quad (3-2)$$

Where, According to Daniels et al. (2019) and Wijnen & Stipdonk, (2016) the *Effectiveness* is typically expressed by means of the percentage reduction (PR) of either the number of crashes or the number of casualties as a consequence of the measure as a consequence of the measure (calculated, for instance, with Crash Modification Factors).

The effectiveness often varies according to the level of severity concerned. The target crashes (*Targetcrashes*) are the number of crashes (or injuries) of various severity levels that possibly can be affected by the measure, so typically in before-after studies this is the estimated number of crashes in the before period corrected for regression to the mean and for trend effects.

The benefits can be expressed in monetary values by multiplying the number of prevented crashes or injuries with the monetary value of the benefit, i.e., the cost per crash or injury (*Crashcost*). Crash costs typically consist of several components of which human costs, i.e., immaterial costs, tend to be the most important. Crash costs are strongly dependent on the severity level of the crash (Daniels et al., 2019; Wijnen & Stipdonk, 2016).

Figure 3-2: Distribution of the responses Adapted from Antoniou (2014)

- c) **Identification and quantification of cost:** Since costs are the second most crucial factor, they should be identified and quantified comprehensively. Section 3.2.1.2 presents different kinds of costs associated with the CBA. However, most cost types are quantitative and must be added together to quantify the total cost associated with the deployed change.
- d) **Discounting and calculating the Net Present Value (NPV):** The quantified costs and benefits must be discounted to counter factors like inflation. The discounting should be carried out with a suitable and well-researched discount rate to achieve the corresponding NPV of both the costs (-) and benefits (+). The following formula can be used to discount the costs and benefits.

$$NPV = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\text{nominal value}}{(1+\text{discount rate})^n} \quad (3-3)$$

Net Present Value of the deployed can be calculated by subtracting NPV_{Costs} from $NPV_{Benefits}$, i.e., $NPV_{RSM} = NPV_{Benefits} - NPV_{Costs}$. The value of the NPV of the costs and benefits decides the validity of the CBA, i.e., the CBA only makes sense iff: $NPV_{RSM} > 0$.

- e) **Calculating BCR:** As described in the preceding sections, BCR is an important metric of CBA. It is calculated by dividing the NPV_{Costs} by $NPV_{Benefits}$. The CBA makes sense iff $BCR > 1$. Thus, a deployed change is considered effective iff $NPV_{RSM} > 0$ and $BCR > 1$.

3.1.2 Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA)

The Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA) is another method to analyse the socioeconomic impact of road safety measures. Methodologically, CEA is closely related to CBA. Sometimes, CEA is considered a variant of CBA (Wesemann, 2000). In CEA, the costs associated with a change deployed are quantified along with the number of fatalities and injuries.

One way of carrying out CEA to evaluate a particular road safety measure is by using Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio (ICER) (Chantith et al., 2021) ICER is also used to rank road safety measures in terms of their effectiveness. Mathematically, ICER is described as:

$$ICER = \frac{ADC}{ADE} \quad (3-4)$$

ADC represents the average change in the budget in the given time interval (the period from no road safety measure till its engagement). In contrast, ADE represents the average change in the number of deaths caused by road crashes during the same time interval. The resultant ICER for each measure is then accounted for along with the four quadrants of the CEA plane shown in Figure 3-3 below.

		Number of Deaths	
		Decrease	Increase
Budget for Road Safety Policy	Increase	Quadrant II ADC > 0, while ADE < 0	Quadrant I ADC > 0, and ADE > 0
	Decrease	Quadrant III ADC < 0, and ADE < 0	Quadrant IV ADC < 0, while ADE > 0

Quadrant II The road safety measure was effective, but still could not reduce the budget.	Quadrant I Road safety policy was not effective at all; resulting in an increase in both the cost and the deaths.
Quadrant III The expected goal. The policy was effective, the number of deaths and the budget decreased.	Quadrant IV The number of deaths increased, while the budget reduced. So, the policy was ineffective.

Figure 3-3 CEA plane (four quadrants) (Chantith et al., 2021)

3.2 Data

3.2.1 Input data

The input data to the component of socioeconomic analysis (SEA) can be categorised into two classes (OECD, 2001), namely:

- Input data to calculate the benefits; and
- Input data to calculate the costs.

Both these classes of input data are described in the sections below.

3.2.1.1 Input data to calculate the benefits

The input data for the component of socioeconomic analysis for calculating the benefits (due to the introduction of road safety measures) primarily consists of multiple Key Performance Indicators (KPIs⁴).

The KPIs present the measurable form of all the benefits that the deployed changes produce. A measurable or objective format of the KPIs enables the monetisation process of the benefits.

Table 3-1 presents the three principal issues or categories, and the corresponding foreseeable KPIs (Chantith et al., 2021; Daniels et al., 2019; Elvik, 2001). The preceding components of project PHOEBE's methodological framework, namely demand modelling, behavioural modelling, traffic microsimulation, and road safety assessment, are set (in proper order and loops) to produce these KPIs. However, it is to be noted that additional KPIs may be added, and the currently listed KPIs can be edited or removed from the list depending on the detailed modelling considerations.

Table 3-1 Principal issues, road safety measures and corresponding KPIs

Nr	Principle issues	Corresponding KPIs
1	Health and Safety	Percentage change in FSI
		Number. of quality-adjusted life years due to uptake of active modes and changes in air quality
		Percentage of travel at 3-star or better by road user type
		Percentage participation in walking, cycling & other forms of active mobility
2	Environment	Percentage change in motorised trips
		Percentage change in non- motorised trips
		Percentage change in carbon emissions and/or fuel consumption
3	Economy	Health sector savings per km (from less trauma / better health etc.)
		Rising cost per quality-adjusted life year due to uptake of active modes and changes in air quality
		Percentage change in economic cost of FSI
		Household savings resulting from uptake of active modes

⁴ The selection of the KPIs is a vital part of the project PHOEBE. In the later phase of the project, the project committee and the respective stakeholders can jointly select the KPIs.

The KPIs listed in Table 3-1 will be calculated before and after introducing the changes. This way, the benefits generated by the changes can be delineated and quantified (monetised), which will further act as the benefit side input data for the SEA component.

3.2.1.2 Input data to calculate costs

The other side of the input data to the SEA component consists of the data describing the overall costs of the changes (Daniels et al., 2019). The cost side can be defined as all the costs involved in setting up the changes, including all the one-time investment and recurring costs implicated in setting up the change. The cost part of the input data is more objective than the benefit part since it includes primarily the investment costs, which can be easily quantified in monetary terms. The input costs can be classified into several categories or types, namely:

- **Initial capital costs:** These costs include all the one-time expenses incurred at the beginning of the project implementing changes, e.g., costs of design, construction, equipment purchases, and installation.
- **Operation and maintenance costs:** These costs include any ongoing costs and recurring expenses required to keep the change operational over time, e.g., inspection costs, repair costs, or improvement costs.
- **Administrative costs:** These costs include any one-time or recurring administrative expenses associated with managing the deployed change over time, e.g., Staff salaries, training, and overhead costs related to the RSM.
- **Monitoring and evaluation costs:** These costs involve the expenses associated with tracking the deployed changes in terms of its effectiveness in providing road safety over time. These costs include expenses for data collection, analysis, and reports on safety evaluation.

3.2.2 Outputs and further analyses

The socioeconomic analysis of deployed changes provides valuable outputs, insights, and information to decision-makers. It also enables further analyses that shed light on the potential impacts, benefits, and costs of implementing the changes. The outputs and the further analyses enabled by the socioeconomic analysis are listed below.

3.2.2.1 Outputs

The outputs of socioeconomic analysis typically include:

- 1 **Net Present Value (NPV):** The NPV is a standard output of socioeconomic analysis (cost-benefit analysis) of any changes (Daniels et al., 2019; Drèze & Stern, 1987). The NPV is a numerical value representing the difference between the present value of the benefits provided by the change and its present cost. A positive NPV indicates that the change is economically viable.
- 2 **Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR):** Like NPV, the BCR is another standard output of the socioeconomic analysis (cost-benefit analysis) of any change. The BCR presents the value of the ratio of the benefits generated by the change deployed to its costs. A BCR > 1 signifies that the benefits generated by the change are more than the costs involved in setting up that change (Daniels et al., 2019; Drèze & Stern, 1987).
- 3 **Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio (ICER):** Like BCR, ICER is the ratio of the average change in the budget in the given time interval, i.e., the period from no deployed change till its engagement to the average change in the number of deaths caused by crashes during the same time interval. The resultant ICER for each change is compared to the four quadrants of the CEA plane to provide its effectiveness (Chantith et al., 2021; Wesemann, 2000). It is an output of the cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA). The CEA plane is presented in Figure 3-3.

- 4 **Monetised benefits and costs:** The socioeconomic analysis provides detailed and quantified information about the benefits and the costs in terms of monetary values (CBA) associated with the deployed change.

3.3 Further analyses

Further analyses supported by SEA that can be carried out following the SEA process are:

- 1 **Sensitivity Analysis:** The sensitivity analysis explores the effects of changing values of the critical assumptions or variables on the results.
- 2 **Other economic (indicators) analyses:** Economic indicators such as the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) calculation can be used to assess the rate of return on investment and the financial attractiveness of the deployed change.
- 3 **Risk assessment analysis:** The risk assessment analysis can provide a qualitative or quantitative assessment of the potential risks and uncertainties associated with the road safety measure's outcomes and costs.
- 4 **Inputs for Policy Decisions:** The analyses of the outputs of the SEA provide critical information for making informed policy decisions. Decision-makers can use the results to prioritise and allocate resources effectively. Additionally, feedback loops can be arranged to control the potency or effectivity of the change to the preceding modules of the project PHOEBE, e.g., mode choice modelling, traffic microsimulation, behavioural modelling, and road safety assessment module.
- 5 **Monitoring and Evaluation Plan:** The SEA outputs can also provide the necessary information in setting up recommendations for a monitoring and evaluation plan to track the actual outcomes of the implemented changes and compare them to the projected benefits and costs.

4 Solution requirements and technical specifications

This section is focused on the existing and 'to become available' techniques and related technologies required for the PHOEBE Framework, and sets out the priorities and related information required for WP3. It includes:

- Technical sheets which outline all the relevant details about each component, such as model descriptions, inputs and outputs, equipment, and license requirements;
- The technological developments for the models' integration and harmonisation of concepts, inputs and parameters and their delivery timetable; and
- Uncertainties and issues to be addressed in WP3.

4.1 Technical sheets

The technical sheets compile technical data about each of the elements in the PHOEBE Framework. The purpose of the technical sheets is to provide a reference to the PHOEBE technical partners to support the development work in WP3 and to facilitate information findings in future applications of the PHOEBE Framework.

The technical sheet content reflects the knowledge of the current stage of PHOEBE development. Therefore, the technical sheets will be updated as the WP3 and the PHOEBE project progresses. The technical sheets are included in the appendices of this document.

4.2 WP3 technical development plan

To put PHOEBE's theoretical methodology into practice, the technical partners must perform a series of activities to achieve the level of technical development necessary to test the proposed theoretical framework.

The activities can be split into three phases: (i) preparation, (ii) development and (iii) integration and refinements. Figure 4-1 presents the main activities in each development phase.

Figure 4-1 WP3 development phases

4.2.1 PHASE I: Preparation (6 months)

Phase I, the preparation phase, aims to set the specificities of the approach. With the definition of the information flows established in the theoretical framework, partners must agree on the technical aspects to successfully receive inputs. Examples of matters that need to be discussed are:

- Network compatibility between traffic simulation models and road safety assessment methods;
- Modal split outlook format to input into traffic simulation; or
- Behavioural parameters that need to be calibrated into traffic simulation models and how to calibrate them.

This phase has some intersections with other work packages. The design of new surveys will be formulated as part of the preparation for model developments but will have close cooperation with the data management efforts handled in WP2. The same is true for the results of the assessments and the information they generated that will be available for other purposes in the project under the umbrella of WP2. Likewise, the Framework needs to calculate the changes in KPIs, theoretically established in this deliverable but also agreed with the local stakeholders as part of the WP4 activities.

Similarly important is the preparation of the traffic microsimulation environment for integration. The simulation tool provided by AIMSUN will be the platform that aggregates the inputs and feed models with their outputs, ensuring the dynamic outputs expected for PHOEBE.

4.2.2 PHASE II: Development (12 months)

The Phase II activity results will determine the suitability and replicability of the PHOEBE predictive approach. It is one of the project's most complex and critical moments because it occurs when the model developments and enhancements are elaborated, calibrated (if that is the case) and tested. This process

is expected to be an iterative, continuous and evolutionary process, where in each round of testing, encounter issues will be worked out to adjust models' statistical and technical fits.

Phase II has a strong alignment with the activities on WP2. In case it is necessary, a continuous process of data delineation is planned to support new data collection. The same is true for WP4, since local stakeholders need to evaluate the project results and provide feedback on the visualisation tool, which will also be developed to allow end users to understand the impacts of testing changes. The visualisation tool will be part of AIMSUN solutions.

Phase II also includes some research aspects. The methodological framework (the 'HOW' matrix together with the process flowchart) serves as a new research and development (R&D) framework too that advances the state-of-the-art and can be used by other scholars for integrating the existing or emerging elements of demand models, traffic microsimulation, road safety assessment, and behavioural models.

However, it is important to note that while the R&D part of the framework may include a broad range of data/models for each of the five components in PHOEBE, not all of them may ultimately be implemented in PHOEBE and only those that are relevant and feasible (particularly with an eye on the use case needs) will be implemented. For example, driving under influence (DUI) is one of the major illegal behaviours among drivers in urban environments and thus may need to be integrated within traffic microsimulation too.

Collecting the data for this behaviour is not a trivial task and may be costly and time consuming. Yet, there is no obstacle in having this behaviour in the R&D part of the project and as a type of illegal behaviours of motorised road users (Section 2.4.2 of this deliverable), especially since the analytical models pertaining to this behaviour may not be substantially different than other relevant behaviours in PHOEBE.

PHOEBE partners have already identified research opportunities within the project scope. Depending on the research findings, the results may or may not be integrated with the final configuration of PHOEBE, but these will be documented and presented in WP3 deliverables.

4.2.3 PHASE III: Integration and refinements (4 months)

Phase III focusses on the integration and possible refinements of the Framework. The complete integration will happen as part of WP5, but WP3 need to develop and test the means of integration.

The PHOEBE Framework will provide a series of supporting materials to ensure replicability. The preparation of the user guides, as well, as the final model development documentation will be performed during Phase III and be part of deliverable D3.2.

4.3 WP3 timeline

The WP3 timeline considers the three phases described above and the project milestones and deliverables planned. The WP GANTT charts are in Appendix B. As highlighted in the timeline (in April 2024 and April 2025), two deliverables need to be prepared respectively to document the technical development work. They are:

D3.1 - New and enhanced models/simulation environments and user support materials (Beta ed.)

D3.1 will present the models' preparations for the use case testing and the upgrades in the simulation environment. The Deliverable D3.1 is considered a mid-term deliverable since the work would still be in progress on the deliverable due date. The nature of the models applied on PHOEBE implies different levels of development at the stage where D3.1 need to be presented. In other words, it is expected that models that are data dependent, such as the demand models and behavioural models, can only be developed entirely after the project achieves the milestone of working data available for WP3, WP4 and WP5, which the due date is the same as that of D3.1.

The D3.1 presentation format is still under discussion but must combine technical documentation and visualisation of upgrades. The deliverable content will present the advances in the simulation environment and the road safety assessments to demonstrate the PHOEBE framework in the use cases.

D3.2 - Finalised models/simulation environments methodology factsheets and user support materials

D3.2 will present the final version of the model, including the refinements and lessons learned as part of the use case demonstration. The user documentation will also be part of D3.2, where the practical and theoretical information to guide the end user in applying the PHOEBE framework will be presented.

4.3.1 PHOEBE development interdependencies

The complexity of the PHOEBE Framework is strongly related to the number of inter-dependencies among its components. The connections and data flows between the elements of the PHOEBE Framework (as depicted in Figure 1-1) are relevant to the project's technical developments. This section describes the interdependencies that need to be resolved in WP3. The technical sheets in Appendix A provide more detail on the technical interdependencies.

Technical specificities to be resolved regarding the interdependencies:

- Definition of dynamic risk profiles (Star Ratings, crash risk scores and/or FSI Estimations); To create the conditions for risk scores to be used in such models, they will be calculated first as static scores based on road AADT and 85th percentile operating speed, representing the overall condition of the network over the day to the models. The results can be updated further in the process after the speed and flow profiles are available for the dynamic risk assessments from the simulations.
- Validity and relevance of Star Ratings as a surrogate measure for safety perception (research and validation required): Although the iRAP Star Rating does not reflect road user perceptions, the characteristics of the infrastructure affect the demand for specific modes (e.g., more cycling trips when cycling infrastructure is available) or the way road users use the infrastructure (e.g., driving close to cyclist when there is road mark separating the flows). Therefore, risk scores must be available before estimating the demand and behavioural models.
- Simulation timeframes and demand data availability: The simulation of the scenarios depends on the flow information in the shape of OD matrix and zoning. Therefore, the demand data's availability will inform the scenarios to be tested as part of PHOEBE (on-peak, off-peak, hourly, or other). AIMUSN Next defines the data parameters well since this is a standard input for traffic simulation scenarios.
- Establishment of calculation procedures to adjust microsimulation behavioural factors: The traffic simulation depends on the individual behavioural probabilities or behavioural parameters in the car-following, lane-changing and gap acceptance models. How the models that describe the target behaviours will be incorporated into the AIMSUN next tool will be discussed in WP3.
- Data transfer procedures from givers to receivers: The PHOEBE integration will be successful if the data flows are well established in data configuration to match receivers' requirements and the flow timeline (in each moment of the flow process, the outputs and inputs should be shared). Each of the interdependencies's arrows presented in Figure 1-1 has its own set of arrangements that need to be made by the pair of partners. The WP3 deliverables will document and describe the data transfer procedures to support further applications of PHOEBE.

- Association of risk scores to the different categorisations of speed and flows: This involves the necessary handling of AIMSUN outputs to attend the requirements of road safety assessments (e.g., calculation of mean speeds), and also the adaptation of road AADT risk scores to hourly based flows.
- Calculation procedure for the FSI Estimations: As previously explained, the PHOEBE framework will predict FSI in two ways: (i) from the iRAP FSI Estimation model based on infrastructure-related crash modification factors and exposure, and (ii) from the number of crashes estimated by analysed behaviour from the surrogate measures outputted from traffic microsimulation. The behavioural crashes will work as an adjustment/calibration factor for the infrastructure-related estimations. The procedures to produce the final PHOEBE output and its major KPI will be resolved and tested as part of the next steps.
- Specifications for risk visualisation for the final estimations of fatality and severe injuries: It is crucial that predicted risk profiles can be visualised within the Aimsun Next platform to allow end users to set new network configurations, inform new changes or policies based on the risk, and test new scenarios which can improve safety. After the simulation runs and the dynamic risk scores are completed, they feed back to AIMSUN Next as a new information layer for users.

4.4 Preparation for models' integration

Aimsun Next has a default set of models that enable to perform microsimulations out of the box. These models that govern vehicular and pedestrian behaviour are updated on regular time intervals. In the Aimsun case, this is any time higher than 0.1s, in increments of 0.1s – typically, on the range from 0.8s to 1.5s. The models to update depend on the user type and are different for either motorised or non-motorised vehicles than for pedestrians.

These default models can be improved or changed, as Aimsun Next is a flexible simulation platform. This means that is possible to integrate the different PHOEBE framework elements. Further, Aimsun is not only able to include new models, but can integrate external data sources and visualise them in a user-friendly manner. This is achieved through a series of interfaces that Aimsun Next has and enables the incorporation of new data, new models or integrations with other tools or models. The tools are: scripting, API, microSDK and an external agent interface. Finally, there are two additional features of Aimsun Next, one that can enable a better result visualisation, the Aimsun view modes; and another to enable unattended simulation runs in batch, the aconsole tool.

4.4.1 Redefinition of existing models

Existing models have lots of parameters to be fine-tuned. This allows that with the same simulation models, different vehicles can be successfully simulated. For instance, vehicles in Aimsun Next use the same set of models with different calibration values. This means that trucks, buses cars, motorbikes or even bicycles can use the same set of models, and it should be possible to integrate e-scooters or other types of vehicles provided that there is data with which to validate. For vehicles there is also lane-based behaviour with the following models: the car-following model, the lane changing model and the gap acceptance mode. There are also non-lane-based models that substitute the first two by a model that provides the 2D vehicle position in the traffic flow. Similarly, a social force model moves pedestrians through the sidewalk and then a pedestrian crossing model is applied when the pedestrian wants to cross vehicular infrastructure. It is also possible to have different types of pedestrians calibrated to model for instance children, adults, and the elderly.

Calibration parameters are not unique to vehicles or pedestrians. They are also present on the network elements like the sections. Thus, sections have different properties, the speed limit being the most

interesting one for PHOEBE, that sets the maximum speed users should drive on that section, or vehicle overtaking on two-way roads, using a two-way two-lane overtaking model.

Finally, some calibration parameters are found at the experiment level, this means that are global and affect all the simulation setup. The main simulation wide calibration parameter is simulation step, which controls how often the objects positions, speed, accelerations are updated, so how fine the simulation resolution is, which by definition is the reaction time of the microsimulation objects (since every time the objects are updated, they react to the latest state of the surrounding objects).

4.4.2 Expansion possibilities and platform integration

To explain how it is possible to expand Aimsun Next, some introduction on the object coding paradigm that Aimsun Next follows is necessary. The key idea is that there are generic classes with a shared set of properties like: cars, trucks, sections, nodes, traffic lights, demand matrices, etc, and object instantiations with particular values. The later are the objects that populate the simulation environment, with for instance as many sections as the road network has, each with their particular number of lanes, length, etc. So whenever there is a need to customise an Aimsun Next simulation, there is the need to look for the object classes that are needed and then redefine some of their values or properties. An overview of the extension tools in Aimsun Next can be found at the online manual: Scripting, API, SDK - Aimsun Next Users Manual.

4.4.2.1 Scripting

Following the previous introduction, all types of objects in Aimsun Next have attributes. These are information values that describe the particular instance of the object. The attribute values can either be something that defines the object in the simulation, like the maximum speed of the vehicle, or data that is stored during the simulation and has multiple values over time like the actual traveling speed of the vehicle. Attributes that have information over time are called time series.

The scripting interface in Aimsun Next offers the possibility to interact with these attributes through the GUI, python or C++. The options are mainly: to create new attributes, retrieve values from existing attributes, write values to attributes and get some related object to the current one, for instance we can know which section a vehicle is now travelling in.

Scripts in the graphical user interface are executed either before or after the simulation but cannot be executed during the simulation. This limits the ability to modify simulation on the go based on some external logic. However, scripting commands are also available in the API, which will be explained in the next section, allowing for the performance of changes in simulation. Thus, scripting can be used as a standalone to introduce static values, in the case of PHOEBE this can be the current static iRAP star ratings, or used as a building block inside the API for further dynamism. Additional content on the scripting technique can be found at the Aimsun online manual: Scripting - Aimsun Next User's Manual.

4.4.2.2 API

API, which stands for Advanced Programming Interface is the option to interact with Aimsun Next simulation models in a customisable but controlled manner. The interaction is limited to a series of callbacks where the API can perform some actions, which in turn are limited to the scripting commands and some API commands to modify in simulation values. This means that control over the simulation while ample, is not total. In micro simulation those calls happen very often. This is before simulation starts, so any values to be initialised before the simulation can be placed here, before and after each simulation step, when a vehicle or pedestrian enters or exits the network, when a vehicle enters or exists a section, when the simulation ends to perform any postprocessing.

More information on the API can be found at the Aimsun online manual: API - Aimsun Next User's Manual, and in particular the following section Aimsun Next Microscopic API - Aimsun Next User's Manual has a

comprehensive list of the functions available to modify the simulation, which for instance has a function to force a given vehicle speed, or to force a vehicle to re-route.

4.4.2.3 microSDK

The Aimsun Next microSDK provides a platform in C++ to replace some of the Aimsun vehicular models with a developer's own model. The microSDK toolkit provides all the functions and information necessary to allow for such developments. It enables full control of the available information in a vehicle and its behaviour. This includes car following, lane changing, acceleration aggressiveness, etc. An alternative to implementing full car-following and/or lane changing methods consists of modifying the key expressions used in the Aimsun Next car-following and lane-changing methods, specifically the acceleration and deceleration speed components and the minimum gap used in the gap acceptance. Further information can be found at the corresponding section of Aimsun Next manual: Micro SDK - Aimsun Next User's Manual.

4.4.2.4 External Agent Interface

The External Agent Interface (EAI) can introduce into an Aimsun Next microscopic simulation externally controlled vehicles and/or pedestrians, (from now on called objects as per the coding nomenclature) can introduce into an Aimsun Next microscopic. Such external objects can be guided by the actions of, for example: a human driver in a simulator, an autonomous vehicle controller, or an experimental control system being tested in a simulation environment.

The data exchanged via the EAI is based on geographic locations expressed as x- and y-coordinates rather than the simulated representation of the traffic network expressed via lanes and turns. This means that the external control logic needs no detailed knowledge of how Aimsun Next models the traffic network – it can continue to use its own network model. Data exchange relies solely on there being a shared system of common coordinates.

External objects are positioned on the network within the simulation. The other objects in the simulation – the ones controlled and updated by Aimsun Next – will then react to the presence of external vehicles by following or avoiding them, collaborating with their movements, and including them in their assessment of gaps at junctions, pedestrian crossings, sections in the same way as they react to other 'internal' objects in the simulation.

As an option, the external application can take control of any object generated by Aimsun Next, in which case Aimsun Next stops updating them, meaning they must be updated by the external application. The external application may also return object ownership to Aimsun Next, in which case Aimsun Next begins to update them again.

Additional information can be found at the corresponding section of the Aimsun Next manual: External Agent Interface - Aimsun Next User's Manual.

4.4.2.5 Aconsole

Finally, the aconsole tool, is a way to launch and interact with simulation experiments from code in a completely unattended fashion. While this option is not recommended for use in launching small numbers of simulations, if any module needs to interact with simulation in an iterative way, or needs to launch a large number of simulations; then the aconsole option is a useful option: Command Line Options - Aimsun Next Users Manual.

4.4.3 Preparing for results visualisation – View modes

View modes are another feature of Aimsun Next, that can be used to visualise both internal data sources, and external data imported using scripting. View modes are the way Aimsun Next displays the objects data into the GUI, and can be customised to show any value in multiple forms, like width, colour, shapes,

etc. This means that any attribute, off-the-shelf or generated via scripting can be displayed in Aimsun Next. Figure 4-2 shows a mock up integration of the iRAP star rating, where a small rural motorway exit has been imported and sections have been assigned a custom iRAP star rating value. A new view mode had been generated to show each value of the star rating with a colour. Further information can be found at Visualising Outputs - Aimsun Next User Manual. The key takeaway of this section is that any attribute that can be linked to an Aimsun object, can be visualised using a view mode.

Figure 4-2 shows an example of using view modes in Aimsun Next. For this example, a mock-up of iRAP Star Rating integration has been setup in a motorway exit.⁵

Figure 4-2 Example visualisation of Star Ratings integrated into an Aimsun Next visualisation of a simulated road network.

⁵ For illustrative purposes only. The Star Rating values shown do not come from any iRAP survey.

5 Conclusions

PHOEBE project aims to create a Framework which can anticipate the safety implications of changes and future scenarios across urban transport networks. This prospective assessment methodology combines road safety assessment, mode shift and induced demand modelling, human behavioural models, and traffic simulation, with a particular focus on vulnerable road users' safety.

This deliverable establishes the theoretical principles and methodological approach of the PHOEBE Framework. The deliverable covers different elements involved, providing insights on “HOW” the different components integrate and interact with each other within the Framework. This includes explanations covering the needs of data, processes, models, and testing requirements, the input-output from one to the other component, and the flow of steps involved.

Further, it describes the main methodological outputs which will form key parts of the Framework, including the dynamic risk profiles and socioeconomic analysis methodology, as well as the visualisation of the results.

The deliverable also sets out a detailed workplan and preparations for WP3 where the research and development activities will take place. It sums up, the technical methods, resources and tools needed to deliver the technical aspects of the project and how the integration of the above aspects including technical specifications and related inter-dependencies are achieved.

For each element of the PHOEBE Framework specifically, this deliverable:

- Sets out the methodology for estimating the mode shift by considering new modes of transport as well as how to incorporate the mode share forecasts into microsimulation modelling through mode choice probabilities.
- Identifies the categories of analytical models (e.g., discrete choice models) for modelling the prioritised behaviours of road users within the PHOEBE project including, in general, road users' unsafe and non-complying behaviours to roadway rules (e.g., drivers' speeding and pedestrians' illegal crossing, aggressive driving) to be incorporated in the microsimulation tool. Additionally, the models (e.g., Bayesian models and EVT models) which by utilising the relevant output from microsimulation and actual crashes can estimate the calibration parameters to be used for dynamic risk scores estimation by the road safety assessment models.
- Explores and identifies the models, extensions and capabilities within microsimulation modelling tools to incorporate the aforementioned (human factors based) behavioural models through necessary coding within the APIs. Additionally, it is also recognised how the output from the microsimulation runs will be used within the road safety assessment models (by using updated flows and speeds) for dynamic road safety assessment.
- Defines the overarching approach and process for dynamic calculation of risk scores from the road safety assessment models through integration with demand, behavioural, and microsimulation models, as well as identifies the suitable safety indicators. Additionally, the need for harmonisation is identified between the road safety assessment models and output from microsimulation models as the safety indicators that are commonly used in road safety assessment (i.e. risk scores) are based on crashes and crash modification factors whereas the safety indicators that are commonly used in traffic microsimulation are based on identification of traffic conflicts by processing the simulated vehicular trajectories in a surrogate safety assessment model.

- Outlines the methodology for socio-economic analysis of the safety impacts under PHOEBE Framework.

A number of research opportunities are identified through the discussions of the PHOEBE Framework. Examples include:

- The necessary methodological improvements in the existing models, especially with regard to incorporating VRUs and introducing new modes of transport such as micro-mobility options into each component of the Framework;
- Finding the most suitable models for implementation within each element; and
- Finding the most optimal way of integrating the models from each component for more accurate and dynamic road safety assessment for all road users.

The PHOEBE Framework will be implemented through three pilot cities including Athens (GR), Valencia (ES), and West Midlands (UK) through testing different urban mobility scenarios. Additionally, through research and development part of the project, further refinement and enhancement of the models within the Framework is envisioned for broader use.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Technical sheets

<p>Models Description</p>	<p>Behavioural Models:</p> <p>Two major modelling techniques for modelling human behaviours will be used including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Discrete Choice Models: These models take the perspective of discrete decision-making processes (e.g. discrete instances of going over the speed limit) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multinomial logit models - Ordered probit models - Random parameters logit/probit models - Latent class logit/probit models ○ Structural Equations Models: These models look at the continuous proportions of behaviours over a certain period of time (the ratio of aggressive mobility over kilometres travelled). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Principal component analysis - Confirmatory factor analysis - Generalised linear models - Latent variable models <p>Three general groups of behavioural models will be developed corresponding with the three human factors prioritised in PHOEBE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Group #1: speeding behaviour of motor vehicles on urban arterials ● Group #2: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ illegal crossing of pedestrians at intersections and/or zebra crossings ○ red-light running of bicycles and e-scooters ● Group #3: harsh manoeuvring (acceleration, deceleration) cornering of drivers and/or cyclists
<p>Expected inputs</p>	<p>Individual driving instances (or proportions) with speed over the speed limit</p> <p>Individual driving instances of violations to roadway regulations (all road user types)</p> <p>Red-light running events (all road user types)</p> <p>J-walking or illegal crossing events</p> <p>Not yielding events (e.g., motorised vehicles not yielding to VRUs)</p> <p>Events of aggressive driving</p> <p>Events of distracted driving (e.g., use of cell phone)</p> <p>Roadway and Traffic Characteristics related data</p>
<p>Input data sources</p>	<p>Cameras</p> <p>Sensors</p> <p>Floating Car Data</p> <p>Telematics</p> <p>Traffic Survey Data</p> <p>Travel Attitudes Survey (could be the source for violations and distracted driving etc.)</p>

Technical sheet

Behavioural Modelling

Expected outputs	Individual probabilities or proportion of the population conducting each of the modelled behaviour Conflicts results in the number of FSI crashes Conflicts caused by the targeted behaviours
PHOEBE Framework Dependencies (what is this dependent on happening before)	Acquiring relevant data from available sources as well as collecting necessary data in the case of unavailability from the available sources (e.g. some useful data for the proposed behavioural models could be collected through the stated/revealed preference surveys)
PHOEBE Framework Predecessors (what does this inform)	Microsimulation models for calibrating the behavioural parameters to be used in the microsimulation models Road safety assessment tools through providing calibration factors for behaviours and estimation of FSI because of the modelled behaviours
Equipment (Software requirements)	Aimsun software Necessary Statistical Analysis Software
License requirements (if any)	Aimsun License License for any particular statistical analysis software (if not already available)
PHOEBE developments	Three general groups of behavioural models will be developed corresponding with the three human factors prioritised in PHOEBE: <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Group #1: Speeding<ul style="list-style-type: none">- speeding behaviour of motor vehicles on urban arterials● Group #2: Violations<ul style="list-style-type: none">- illegal crossing of pedestrians at intersections and/or zebra crossings- red-light running of bicycles and e-scooters● Group #3: Harsh manoeuvring<ul style="list-style-type: none">- acceleration, deceleration, cornering of drivers and/or cyclists
Additional information	Detailed information about the behavioural models can be found in PHOEBE Deliverable 1.2.

Technical sheet

Traffic Simulation

Models Description	<p>Aimsun simulation platform</p> <p>Aimsun provides a comprehensive simulation software. It includes all the relevant aspects in traffic simulation: network representation, traffic lights control, demand modelling, different user behaviour modelling, traffic routing, public transportation and pedestrians among the most relevant. On top of that the software offers various coding capabilities to expand their functionality using ad-hoc solutions.</p> <p>Aimsun default models</p> <p>Aimsun software platform has a wide variety of models to achieve a comprehensive simulation software. For PHOEBE project the most relevant are those related to traffic dynamics, these are the car following model, Modelling Vehicle Movement - Aimsun Next User's Manual. Then in multi lane streets or roads, the lane changing model Modeling Vehicle Movement - Aimsun Next User's Manual, and in unsignalised intersections the gap acceptance model Modelling Vehicle Movement - Aimsun Next User's Manual. Last but not least the pedestrian model driven by a social force model that enables or simulate individuals pedestrians Simulating Pedestrians - Aimsun Next User's Manual and Gap Acceptance Model for Pedestrians at Traffic Signals - Aimsun Next User's Manual.</p>
Expected inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Network general geometric data: To set up a simulation model a representation of the network is required, including the links, nodes and turnings. This can be imported from various sources or preexisting simulation models.● Traffic light operational features: traffic lights timing and control schemes need to be introduced into the simulation platform.● Demand data: origin destination matrices by transportation mode are required.● Public transportation: if any effects of the public transportation vehicles moving through the network are required, then the public transportation data, including, paths, stops and schedule are needed. Open GTFS is typically enough.● Traffic flow data: in order to validate traffic models, at least traffic flow count at some key locations is needed, speeds and density or occupancy values are appreciated.● Behavioural data: for highly detailed model calibration users' behavioural data like trajectories, acceleration or speed profiles are necessary.
Input data sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Open-source data: network information can be gathered from OSM, public transportation from GTFS, an many times there are public AADT.● Project partners: are expected to provide detailed data like Origin Destination matrices and complimentary data to the open-source data.

Technical sheet

Traffic Simulation

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Use case stakeholders: are expected to provide details on the infrastructure changes to model and some additional data to enrich the data already obtained from open source and project partners.
Expected outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Calibrated simulation models: Aimsun Next simulation models to assess the what if scenarios around the zones of interest.● Dynamic traffic parameters: from the simulation models the three main traffic variables will be available as time series (fluctuating over time). These are: flow, speed and density.● Vehicles trajectories: this will enable an in-detail analysis of the conflicts that arise at different places of the network as well as the use of Surrogate Safety Measures with software packages like SSAM.
PHOEBE Framework Dependencies (what is this dependent on happening before)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Data: to develop the Aimsun models a significant amount of data is required, this is already explained in the expected inputs, but the PHOEBE framework dependencies are:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ iRAP star rating data○ Mode choice models● Behavioural models: calibration of simulation models is dependent on the behavioural models used to perform the simulation; thus, modelling cannot be completed until the behavioural models to use are fully developed.
PHOEBE Framework Predecessors (what does this inform)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● iRAP dynamic star rating: to develop dynamic star rating, simulation is needed to test different scenarios.● Mode choice iterations: to assess the optimal mode choice split the simulation platform needs to be ready.
Equipment (Software requirements)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Aimsun Next 23● Python 3.10 and the optional libraries needed (this will depend on the PHOEBE project development)
License requirements (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Adequate Aimsun licence. Aimsun is a proprietary software that needs a licence to be used. There are different tiers of licences, depending on the modules needed
PHOEBE developments	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Simulation model with integrated PHOEBE modules<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Simulation model development○ Integration of new behavioural models○ Integration of the mode choice model○ Integration of the iRAP star ratings into a simulation platform○ Integration of the new dynamic star rating

Models Description	<p>Discrete choice models:</p> <p>The discrete choice models will be deployed to forecast the mode choice of the individual scenarios, including the modal shift between two scenarios. Discrete choice models specify the probability of choosing an alternative (out of all the alternatives available) by a group of individuals (out of all the groups under consideration). A suitable model type will be chosen, considering the input data.</p>
Expected inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Stated-Preference (SP) survey data: The SP survey data (stated preference) will be an essential input to the model. Through the stated preference surveys, hypothetical situations are presented to the respondents, who are then asked to choose based on the given attributes for each alternative without necessarily experiencing them in real situations. ● Revealed Preference (RP) data: The RP data capture travellers' current or revealed travel behaviour. For instance, one is interested in knowing the mode a traveller uses, travel times, and destinations. ● Travel diaries: A travel diary is an individual's record of his or her travels. This essentially is a type of revealed data. ● Telematics data: The telematics data capturing location, speed, fuel consumption, vehicle faults, etc., will be used as inputs for the model. ● Demographic data: Demographic data containing details like age, gender, location, household information, car availability, etc., will be used as input for the model. ● Count data: Count data, e.g., the number of vehicle trips, vehicle miles travelled, the number of person miles travelled, etc., will be used for calibrating the model.
Input data sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SP data: The SP data will be gathered from surveys. ● RP data: The RP data can be gathered from several sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● From travellers' travel diaries ● Operational data revealing the preferences of the travellers from the road authorities ● Travel diaries: From surveys. ● Telematics data: From professional data providing companies, local authorities. ● Demographic data: From local authorities, census etc. ● Count data: From professional data providing companies, local authorities.
Expected outputs	<p>The model is expected to deliver the probabilities of choosing different alternatives by different groups of individuals. These probabilities can then be used to generate the OD matrices for all the individual groups using all the alternatives.</p>

Technical sheet

Mode choice and modal shift models

PHOEBE Framework Dependencies (what is this dependent on happening before)	<p>Before model estimation: The models have a dependency on the quality and type of the input data.</p> <p>After model estimation: After model estimation, the calibration of the model depends on the quality and type of the count data.</p> <p>Interscenario dependencies: The models will have dependencies on all the steps and models that can alter the input or explanatory variables of the mode choice models, e.g., Travel time, cost, number of transfers, speed etc.</p>
PHOEBE Framework Predecessors (what does this inform)	Surveys and other input data.
Equipment (Software requirements)	<p>BIOGEME: Python- and Pandas-based open-source software.</p> <p>Apollo: R-based open-source package.</p> <p>MS Excel, AIMSUN (travel demand modelling software)</p>
License requirements (if any)	AIMSUN
PHOEBE developments	<p>As part of the PHOEBE developments, the mode choice models are planned to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Reflect the multidimensionality of human behaviour while choosing modes, e.g., personal preferences, socioeconomic characteristics, attitudes, cultural influences, driver characteristics, response times, adaptation behaviours, and psychological factors.● Incorporate the perception of risks associated with modes while choosing modes.● Reflect the spatiotemporal characteristics of mode choice.● Incorporate the effects of the real-time information flow through apps and internet in mode choice.● Incorporate the VRUs in mode choice framework.

<p>Models Description</p>	<p>iRAP Star Rating Methodology</p> <p>Road inspection data to provide a simple and objective measure of the level of safety 'built-in' to the roads for vehicle occupants, motorcyclists, pedestrians and bicyclists.</p> <p>iRAP Fatal and Severe injuries estimation methodology</p> <p>Fatal and Serious Injury (FSI) Estimates draw on the road attribute data used for Star Ratings, flow data for each road user and network-level crash data to provide an estimation of FSIs along each segment of a road and support localised prioritisation of investment.</p> <p>CycleRAP</p> <p>Road safety risk model for bicycle and light mobility users to evaluate the risk of incidents of road and bicycling infrastructure.</p>
<p>Expected inputs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enriched Geometry data: encoded road-related attributes each detailing the immediate road environment and risk influencing attributes for road segments. The attributes to be recorded can be found on the iRAP Coding Manual (left hand drive and right hand drive versions). • Operational data: speed and flows Guidelines on how to traditionally collect speed and flow data for static Star Rating analysis can be found at iRAP Survey Manual. • Georeferenced crash data by road user category (vehicle occupants, motorcyclists, pedestrians and bicyclists) and crash type (run-off passenger and driver side, head-on for loss of control or overtaking, intersection, property access, along, crossing inspected or intersected road). Crash data input format can be found at the iRAP Star Rating and Investment Plan Manual Road user category and crash types considered in the analysis can be found at iRAP Methodology Fact Sheet #4 Crash types
<p>Input data sources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Road feature data recorded from video survey or from an AiRAP data supplier • Operational data on speed and flows can be taken from local authority data when present, road operation measurement or use of data suppliers providing measured speed and flow data (for example The Flow or O7 may provide measures road speed or other data to support the model) • Crash data from road authorities <p>All data need to be compatible with iRAP specification available at: https://irap.org/specifications/</p> <p>More details on the input data for the PHOEBE project can be found at PHOEBE Deliverable 2.1 - Consolidated data requirements and use case region data availability report.</p>

Technical sheet

Road Assessment Methodology

Expected outputs	<p>Risk scores and fatal and severe injuries per user type (car occupant, motorcyclists, pedestrians, and bicyclists) per crash type (run-off passenger and driver side, head-on for loss of control or overtaking, intersection, property access, along, crossing inspected or intersected road) every 100m and compatibilised with simulation nodes and links.</p> <p>Mapping risk scores and FSIs estimations</p> <p>Detailed catalogue road attributes (100m links or for nodes/links).</p>
PHOEBE Framework Dependencies (what is this dependent on happening before)	<p>Static risk scores: none</p> <p>Dynamic risk scores: Star Rating models will receive inputs of speed and flows from traffic simulation. Fatal and severe injuries estimation will be calibrated based on behavioural model results.</p>
PHOEBE Framework Predecessors (what does this inform)	<p>Demand models: To be completed</p> <p>Behaviour models</p> <p>Traffic simulation tool</p>
Equipment (Software requirements)	<p>ViDA: ViDA is a suite of online tools for calculating, managing, analysing, and presenting Star Ratings and Investment Plans. ViDA provides tools, services, and workflows to manage the RAP data lifecycle, from initial dataset pre-processing to on-screen and downloadable reports. ViDA also allows users to drill down through and analyse assessments using a flexible filter and search tool. ViDA requires users to register for a ViDA account. Registration is free and only needs to be done once. More information can be found at: https://vida.irap.org</p> <p>iRAP API: iRAP API is used to connect third entities to the ViDA services. There are two classes for connecting to the API. The first, App(), can be used to make requests that don't require user authentication, such as requesting a user token. The second, User() is used for other requests. In order to access a particular resource or method, the third entity must have permission to use it. Permissions are set up by iRAP, based on agreements on inputs and outputs. More information can be found at https://github.com/iRAP-software/package-vida-api-sdk</p>
License requirements	<p>iRAP protocols are supported in a charitable framework which are free to use. IP remains with iRAP. iRAP activities require specialist skills and knowledge. iRAP strongly recommends training for people preparing to undertake an iRAP project. Information about the training courses available can be found on the iRAP website, at https://www.irap.org/training.</p> <p>ViDA: Anyone using the protocols need to agree to ViDA terms and conditions (https://vida.irap.org/en-gb/terms).</p> <p>API: In order for you to use the ViDA API, you must agree to the terms and conditions available by request.</p>

Technical sheet

Road Assessment Methodology

PHOEBE developments	<p>As part of the PHOEBE developments, the iRAP protocols will be enhanced to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">I. Allow risk models to work in conjunction with traffic simulation tools by network compatibilisation among 100m link to links/nodes and protocols to calculate results (risk scores and FSIs for the new metrics).II. Define the best road safety metrics for the traffic simulation (risk score, star ratings, or other)III. Account for variable speed and flows for different periods of time (peak/off-peak, hourly based, and others)IV. Develop a method to calibrate the estimated FSIs based on behavioural related estimated crashes.V. Establish procedures to connect models with iRAP ViDA system.VI. Demonstrate the use of CycleRAP in microsimulation of new designs.VII. Support visualisation of risk scores/star ratings or FSIs in macro/micro simulation environments
Additional information	<p>Detailed information about the iRAP methodology can be found at</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• PHOEBE Deliverable 1.1 - SoA and end user needs review• iRAP Specifications Webpage• iRAP Methodology Webpage

<p>Module Description</p>	<p>Socioeconomic analysis (SEA) module: The module of SEA consists of multiple sub-modules. These sub-modules include several analytical models which will be deployed for:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scaling (up/down) model: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Scaling up the KPIs (for calculating the benefits of mobility and environmental impacts including the number of fatalities) for the whole network produced by the preceding modules, namely, mode choice modelling, traffic microsimulation, behavioural modelling, and road safety assessment. b. Scaling up the Willingness-to-Pay (WTP) to reduce traffic risks and Value of Statistical Life (VoSL) for the valuation of preventing unit traffic fatality (for calculating the benefits of the crashes avoided by the Road Safety Measures (RSM)). 2. Cost and benefit estimation and quantification models: Concerning models for estimating and quantifying the costs and benefits generated by the RSMs. These models include the empirical models for quantifying all the costs and the benefits related to the mobility and environmental impacts and discrete choice models for calculating the WTP to reduce traffic risks and estimating VoSL. 3. SEA model (Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA), Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA)): Concerning empirical models for calculating the socioeconomic impacts due to the RSM. e.g., CBA or CEA.
<p>Expected inputs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Stated-Preference (SP) survey data: The SP survey data (stated preference) will be an essential input to the model for estimating the crash costs (WTP and VOSSL). Through the stated preference surveys, hypothetical situations are presented to the respondents, who are then asked to choose based on the given attributes for each alternative without necessarily experiencing them in real situations. ● Revealed Preference (RP) data: The RP data capture travellers' current or revealed behaviour related to the WTP for risk reduction due to road crashes. ● KPIs: A set of KPIs produced by the preceding modules delivering the information, e.g., Number of crash reduction, Change in travel time, etc. These KPIs will encompass both baseline and proposed scenarios to determine the difference between the baseline and the proposed scenario. ● Cost database: A suitable cost database encompassing all the standard costs related to the proposed RSMs for the corresponding cost calculation.
<p>Input data sources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SP data: The SP data will be gathered from surveys. ● RP data: The RP data can be gathered from several sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● From travellers' travel diaries ● Operational data revealing the preferences of the travellers from the road authorities

Technical sheet

Socioeconomic analysis module

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● KPIs: Preceding modules in the framework.● Cost database: Previous scientific works/projects and standards.
Expected outputs	<p>The module is expected to deliver the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Net present value (For costs, benefits and the RSM).● Benefit Cost ratio.● Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio.● Monetised benefits and costs.● Feedback loops to the preceding modules for updating the assumptions of the RSMs depending on the outputs mentioned above.
PHOEBE Framework Dependencies (what is this dependent on happening before)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Successful running of all the preceding sections or modules in order to produce the KPIs (other modules)● WTP calculation and VoSL estimation (Within the module)
PHOEBE Framework Predecessors (what does this inform)	All the preceding modules through feedback loops on the effectiveness of the RSMs.
Equipment (Software requirements)	BIOGEME: Python- and Pandas-based open-source software. Apollo: R-based open-source package. MS Excel, AIMSUN (travel demand modelling software)
License requirements (if any)	AIMSUN
PHOEBE developments	

Appendix B:

WP3 GANTT charts

GANTT chart for mode shift and induced demand modelling

GANTT chart for behavioural modelling

Activity description	Preparation for developments				Development								Integration and refinements										
	Jul-23	Aug-23	Sep-23	Oct-23	Nov-23	Dec-23	Jan-24	Feb-24	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24	Jul-24	Aug-24	Sep-24	Oct-24	Nov-24	Dec-24	Jan-25	Feb-25	Mar-25	Apr-25	
Define the road users' behaviours for modelling (discuss data needs, practicalities, caveats etc.)	█																						
Delineate data needs, find out what's available and what needs to be collected)	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█									
Discussing with Aimsun for identifying the possibilities and necessary actions for incorporating the road users' behaviours (from step 1)		█	█	█	█																		
Discussing with TUM for incorporating questions related to the road users' behaviours and finalising the set of questions for the proposed surveys		█	█	█																			
Discussing with iRAP for incorporating behavioural models in the road safety assessment			█	█	█																		
Planning for necessary data collection (both retrieving from online sources and collecting field data if necessary) and distribution of the proposed surveys (per use			█	█	█																		
Obtaining the necessary data as planned in the previous step (after data collection phase) in coordination with WP4			█	█	█																		
Data preparation and pre-processing , once the data start to become available (data partners)					█	█	█	█	█	█													
Development of the behavioural models (statistical and econometric models)					█	█	█	█	█	█													
Testing of the developed behavioural models based on empirical data (for each use case) and necessary modifications									█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█				
Demonstration through Aimsun microsimulation models and iRAP, and further refinements based on the results									█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█				
Documentation within D3.1							█	█	█														
Establish necessary guidelines for users, supporting material, documentation												█	█	█	█	█	█	█					
Prepare relevant sections within D3.2																			█	█	█		
Development of behavioural models for broader use									█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
Testing the broader behavioural models									█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
Dissemination of results (publications)																					█	█	█

GANTT chart for road safety assessment enhancements – Part 1

Activity description	Preparation for developments				Development								Integration and refinements										
	Jul-23	Aug-23	Sep-23	Oct-23	Nov-23	Dec-23	Jan-24	Feb-24	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24	Jul-24	Aug-24	Sep-24	Oct-24	Nov-24	Dec-24	Jan-25	Feb-25	Mar-25	Apr-25	
Define of the areas of analysis	█																						
Plan and execute survey		█	█																				
Coding data			█	█	█																		
Input supporting data					█	█																	
Generate static star ratings for the use cases						█	█	█	█														
Generate dynamic risk scores for the use cases										█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█				
Generate dynamic fatal and severe injuries for the use cases										█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█				
Documentation within D3.1							█	█	█														

GANTT chart for road safety assessment enhancements – Part 2

Activity description	Preparation for developments				Development								Integration and refinements										
	Jul-23	Aug-23	Sep-23	Oct-23	Nov-23	Dec-23	Jan-24	Feb-24	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24	Jul-24	Aug-24	Sep-24	Oct-24	Nov-24	Dec-24	Jan-25	Feb-25	Mar-25	Apr-25	
Establish way to risk work in conjunction with simulation tools (network matching)	█	█	█																				
Establish procedure to calculate dynamic star ratings - Agree on input data format and type of speed			█	█	█																		
Implementation of the procedure to calculate dynamic star ratings - Prepare modification on coding file and ViDA system to calculate dynamic star ratings					█	█	█	█	█														
Establish and implement procedure to calculate dynamic star ratings - Agree on data transfer procedures										█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█					
Implementation of the procedure to calibrate FSI based on behaviour inputs										█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█						
Define requirements for results visualization							█	█	█														
Visualization tool												█	█	█	█	█	█	█					
Prepare users documentation																				█	█	█	
Documentation within D3.2																				█	█	█	
R&D Crash modification factors to particular road features – Driver modelling based on the risk (change in probability based on the risk)																█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
R&D Establish procedures to calculate CycleRAP FSIs											█	█	█	█									
R&D Star Ratings for e-scooters											█	█	█	█									

GANTT chart for traffic microsimulation enhancements

Activity description	Preparation for developments				Development								Integration and refinements										
	Jul-23	Aug-23	Sep-23	Oct-23	Nov-23	Dec-23	Jan-24	Feb-24	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24	Jul-24	Aug-24	Sep-24	Oct-24	Nov-24	Dec-24	Jan-25	Feb-25	Mar-25	Apr-25	
Preparation of the simulation environment	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█		█	█	█										
Association of the iRAP star Ratings - static	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█														
Association of the iRAP star Ratings - dynamic											█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█					
Association of mode shift and induced demand models							█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█					
Association of behavioural models							█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█					
Run integration trial 1											█	█											
Run integration trial 2																	█	█	█	█	█	█	
Visual representation tool																█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
Methodology factsheet and support materials																					█	█	█
Simulation environment finalised																						█	█

